

The Semantics of Comparative Constructions in Jula (Manding; Burkina Faso)

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Abbreviations and Glosses

CONJ	Conjunction
COP	Copula
EMP	Emphatic
EVAL	Evaluative
FACT	Factive
HAB	Habitual
INF	Infinitive
MF	Measure Function
MP	Measure Phrase
NOM	Nominalizer
LF	Logical Form
LIT	Literal
OP	Operator
PART	Partitive
PFV	Perfective
PL	Plural
POS	Positive
POSS	Possessive
POSTP	Postposition
PRO	Pronoun
SG	Singular
SOV	Subject-Object-Verb
SUBJ	Subject
TAM	Tense-Mood-Aspect
TOP	Topic

Zusammenfassung auf Deutsch

Komparative sind wieder in den Fokus des Interesses gerückt, insbesondere bei den formalen Semantikern. Die Daten zu den Jula-Komparativen tragen zu einem weitreichenden Rätsel bei, bei dem etablierte Annahmen fortbestehen, die jedoch revidiert werden müssen. Im Einklang mit dem kompositionellen Ansatz in der Semantik liefere ich unterstützende Belege zur Syntax-Semantik-Schnittstelle von phrasalen Komparativen und Komparativoperatoren sowie zur Semantik von abstufbaren Prädikaten im Bereich der Negation und Polarität. Bestehende Annahmen über die phrasale Natur von Überschreitungs-komparativen sind für die Jula-Daten nicht haltbar, und eine Darstellung mit einer 3-stelligen Semantik kann die vorgestellten Konstruktionen nicht adäquat erklären. Stattdessen schlage ich vor, die Exceed-Komparative als 2-stellige Operatoren zu behandeln. Konstruktionen mit Differenzialkomparativen, Subkomparativen und Gradvergleichen zeigen, dass Jula eine Gradsemantik besitzt. Anhand ähnlicher Diagnosen wie Howell für Yoruba (2013) habe ich zudem Beweise erbracht, dass Jula eine Gradabstraktion aufweist, obwohl es keine Mehrdeutigkeiten im Geltungsbereich gibt. Mit diesen beiden Makroparametern können die Jula-Daten mit einer einheitlichen 2-Stellen-Analyse, die auf dem Gradvergleich basiert, erklärt werden. Diese einheitliche Analyse wird durch detaillierte Beschreibungen und formale Analysen der Syntax und Semantik der expliziten und impliziten Konstruktionen in Jula auf kompositionelle Weise gestützt.

1 Introduction

Considerable attention in the last decade has gone to researching the underlying semantics of comparative constructions by formal semanticists. There is substantial cross-linguistic variation in the way languages express comparison and the operators associated with comparatives (Beck 2009; Bhatt & Takahashi 2011; Heim 1985, 2001; inter alia) as well as the denotations of the gradable predicates that they combine with (Bochnak 2015; Kennedy 2007b). The constructions under investigation in this thesis come from Jula (Mande; Manding), a language spoken in Burkina Faso and Ivory coast that expresses comparison by way of an exceed-comparative. Exceed-comparatives encode the greater-than relation verbally instead of making use of dedicated comparative morphology (Stassen 1985). An example from Jula is given in (1).

- (1) *Mary ka jan ka tɛmɛ Hawa kan.*
Mary COP tall INF **surpass** Hawa POSTP.
'Mary is taller than Hawa.'
(Lit.) 'Mary is tall **exceeding** Hawa.'

Tɛmɛ is the lexical verb encoding the comparative relation in (1), and denotes the sense of *surpass*. The verb takes a subject and an object, constituting the comparee and comparison standard respectively. A comparative establishes an ordering relation between two individuals, or an individual and a degree, making reference to a measurement scale, such as height (Hohaus & Bochnak 2020). The relevant arguments for explicit comparison are illustrated in (2).

- (2) *Lily_{comparee} is tall_{dimension}er_{comparative operator} than Annika_{comparison standard}.*

In this respect, similarities can be observed to English comparatives like (3), whereby (3) is simply a paraphrase of (2).

- (3) *Lily exceeds Annika in height.*

(2) describes a relation where the degree of Lily's height exceeds the degree of height that Annika holds. Encoding comparison by way of dedicated morphology is common in many Indo-European languages, like English. In contrast, West-African and many Asian languages i.e. Mandarin, often adopt the *exceed*-type comparative construction as the typical pattern (Stassen 1985). Encoding comparison via functional morphology is comparatively less widespread when viewed on a broader scale, but is subject to substantially more investigation than its verbal-strategy counterpart.

Comparatives make reference to a dimension, whereby the adjective is taken to denote a relation between individuals and degrees and the data is analyzed committing to a degree-based approach (Cresswell 1976; Stechow 1984; Heim 1985; Kennedy 1997; inter alia). The mapping of degree, individuals and dimension is distinct to other languages in Jula and I assume an underlying semantic structure differing from the norm for gradable predicates and comparatives.

Three points are central throughout this work: I propose a unified semantic analysis for explicit comparatives in Jula that deviates from the standard accounts of phrasal comparative analyses. I distinguish between explicit and implicit comparatives and motivate the distinction with corresponding diagnostic criteria. Exceed-comparatives are analyzed as phrasal comparatives in the literature. Whether a comparative is phrasal or clausal depends on the type of the than-complement and the material it contains. Secondly, scrutiny is given to the underlying semantics of gradable predicates. The data suggests the presence of a positive operator that encodes a contextual threshold in unmodified adjective phrases as in (4) (Seuren 1978; Stechow 1984; Kennedy 2007).

(4) *Lily_{comparee} is <POS> tall.*

von Stechow (1984) recognizes that unmodified adjective constructions inherently have a contextual comparison layer denoted by a positive operator modifying the adjective. In (4) Lily necessarily needs to reach a contextual threshold of tallness for the sentence to be felicitous. Rett (2007) argues for the availability of this evaluation in other constructions like equatives, measure phrases and question phrases. In every case this is a feature of adjectives and APs and does not necessarily apply to gradable predicates which are derived from i.e. verbs, as is the case in many African languages. However, in Jula I find that some adjectives are in fact true adjectives and not derived from verbs, as they similar to English adjectives also encode a contextual threshold.

1.1 Overview

(5)-(10) illustrate the comparative constructions investigated in Jula. A comparative usually consists of a predicate, a comparison standard and a comparative operator either constructed with dedicated degree morphology, periphrastic constructions, or a verb. The lexical verbs *tɛmɛ* and *dan* encode the comparative relation in Jula and denote the sense of 'surpass'. I will argue that both take two arguments. They differ in regard to the type of their arguments.

Tɛmɛ comes in two variants. The first is embedded in a subordinated infinitival clause, either headed by an adjectival matrix predicate (5), or by an adverbial predicate (6). In the adverbial construction the adverb that supplies the dimension of comparison is often implicit. Secondly, *tɛmɛ* may appear bare, preceded by a habitual marker (or other markers) and a nominalized subject, comparing complex nouns and degrees (7).

- (5) *Hawa ka kɔrɔ ka tɛmɛ Mina kan.*
 Hawa COP old INF **surpass** Mina POSTP.
 'Hawa is older than Mina.'
 (Lit.) 'Hawa is old surpassing Mina.'

- (6) *Fofana be jādilan gnanama ka tēme Kofi kan.*
 Fofana HAB paint beautiful INF **surpass** Kofi POSTP.
 ‘Fofana paints more beautifully than Kofi.’
 (Lit.) ‘Fofana paints beautifully surpassing Kofi.’

- (7) *Audu jan-ya be tēme 1.80m kan.*
 Audu tall-NMLZ HAB **surpass** 1.80m POSTP.
 ‘Audu is taller than 1.80m.’
 (Lit.) ‘Audu’s height surpasses 1.80m.’

Dan is a full predicate and the main verb in a construction whose arguments are restricted to complex nouns, comprised of individuals and nominalized properties headed by a possessive phrase, or degree descriptions (8). The possessive in complex nouns consisting of a relational noun (alienable) like *depth* or *height* combined with an individual are usually covert.

- (8) *Ji dun-ya be 2m dan.*
 Water deep-NMLZ HAB 2m **surpass**.
 ‘The water is deeper than 2m.’
 (Lit.) ‘The water’s depth surpasses 2m.’

(5), (6) (7) and (8) per definitionem make use of dedicated verbal morphology, thereby showing a clear feature of explicit comparison. (9) and (10) have no dedicated degree morphology or other periphrastic constructions, but instead make use of comparison that is not overtly expressed by a verb and can be modified by context. (9) and (10) are implicit comparative constructions. Further details about the differentiation between explicit and implicit will be given in the background section.

- (9) *Hawa ka jan ni Fofana ye.*
 Hawa COP tall CONJ Fofana POSTP
 ‘Hawa is taller than Fofana.’
 (Lit.) ‘Hawa is tall compared with Fofana.’

- (10) *Ka Fofana jati, Hawa ka jan.*
 INF Fofana consider Hawa COP tall
 (Lit.) ‘Considering Fofana, Hawa is tall.’

‘Ni’ is a conjunction that receives a comparative interpretation in combination with adjectives. The implicit comitative construction rigidly consists of ‘Ni...ye’.

1.2 Goal and Outline

This thesis will contribute to the data on comparatives in under-researched languages. I offer new insights into the semantics of exceed-comparatives that may prove useful cross-linguistically.

The syntax-semantics mapping of exceed-comparatives in the literature hinges on the association of phrasal comparatives with 3-place operators. The standard account maps a phrasal comparative with a 3-place semantics (Heim 1985; Beck 2012; Bhatt & Takahashi 2011). The operator takes three arguments, two individuals and a predicate of degrees and individuals. On the other hand, clausal comparatives receive a 2-place mapping; the operator takes two arguments. The Jula data is not adequately described with this syntax-semantics mapping. I question the standard account and suggest a mapping of the phrasal exceed-comparative with a 2-place semantics. The unified 2-place analysis aligns with accounts that favor the optionality of an n-place semantic mapping for phrasal and clausal comparatives (Bhatt & Takahashi 2011; Bochnak 2018).

I formulate the three central claims in this thesis. Each will be discussed in detail, backed by relevant literature, and underlined by formal analyses. Firstly, I claim that exceed-comparatives have a 2-place semantics and propose a unified compositional semantic analysis for all explicit constructions in Jula. Secondly, I claim that the positive operator, first coined by Cresswell (1976) and described in detail by several authors (Stechow 1984; Kennedy 2007ab; *inter alia*) can be found in APs in Jula as well and is a reliable diagnostic to determine "true" adjectives. The consequences these claims have for the analysis of gradable predicates, exceed-comparatives, and antonyms, and the implications for linguistic theory are discussed in the general section. Lastly, the exceed-construction in Jula combines freely with adjectives of positive and negative polarity, a circumstance that possibly arises as a result of syntactic restraints and blocking effects.

1. Unified analysis of Jula exceed comparatives as 2-place operators that compare two degrees.
2. APs in Jula are also evaluative and POS can distinguish true adjectives in Jula from verbal derivatives.
3. 'Exceed' felicitously combines with negative antonyms as a result of syntactic restraints and blocking effects.

The outline of the thesis continues as follows: Section 2 will provide a background in degree semantics and highlight topics concerning explicitness and implicitness, the syntax-semantics interface of comparatives, the underlying structure and scale polarity of gradable predicates, and evaluativity. Section 3 discusses the cross-linguistic variation of exceed-comparatives and reviews recent and relevant literature regarding the syntax and semantics of exceed-comparatives in African languages. The sections 4 and 5 are an in-depth analysis of Jula comparatives, divided into explicit and implicit constructions, supported by relevant literature from 3. Section 6 briefly describes superlative and equative constructions, drawing inferences in light of the insights gained

from the analysis of comparatives. A general discussion in 7 addresses questions that arose during the analysis, and those left for future research. Furthermore, I discuss the implications for linguistics theory and comparatives in general, based on the results of the analyses. A brief conclusion is given in 8.

1.3 Jula Language Facts and Methodology

Jula belongs to the Mande language family and is spoken by roughly 2.2 million people as a first language and 10 million as a second language mainly in Burkina Faso and Ivory Coast. Jula is closely related and mutually intelligible with Bambara and Malinke, both languages that have received some linguistic attention (Koopman 1992; Creissels 2005, 2013; Dumestre 2003). Jula has influences from French and Arabic, with assimilated loan words from both languages, most prominent in this thesis the meaning of *temε* as ‘surpass’ from the French ‘surpasser’ (parallel to ‘exceed’).

The data has been elicited over multiple sessions conducted with native speakers over several months. Acceptability judgments of comparative phrases in varying contexts in addition to translations of phrases have guided the investigation. A baseline was first established from which I progressed to more specific questions about the individual phenomena. I managed to elicit the different constructions in Jula that are used to express comparison by providing specific contexts. Simultaneously, I gained insight as to their distribution and syntax. This data and relevant literature formed the foundation that motivated the formal analysis, whilst adhering to language specific patterns under consideration of local variations in the language.

1.3.1 Syntax and Grammaticalization

Influences from Arabic and French as well as grammaticalization processes have shaped grammatical markers and morphosyntactic structures in Jula. However, some inferences to original patterns can be drawn by looking at similar structures in Bambara (closely related and mutually intelligible). Extensive research on the morphology and syntax of Mande languages has been conducted by Creissels (2020). The overview of Mande languages and their structures provides evidence for grammaticalization effects in languages across Manding regions.

Jula, like the majority of Mande languages is isolating (Vydrin 2018). Inflectional morphology is limited, but the language has a rich derivational system. Morphological case is not assigned, but instead features like suffixation and productive compounding are used extensively (Creissels 2020). Adjectives are not plentiful and predicative descriptive situations are often expressed verbally or in nominalized form. In compounding, it can be the case that verbal lexemes occur as event nouns or even as the second nominalized argument (gerund) (Creissels 2020).

Jula marks tense, aspect, and mood by predicative markers that indicate constituent boundaries and also express a positive vs. negative distinction (Creissels 2005). The constituent order in a verb clause is S pm O V X, where pm is a predicative marker, x denotes an oblique object,

and TAM-markers express grammatical categories. Within adpositional phrases, postpositions, instead of prepositions, are the rule (11) (Kiemtoré 2022).

	Subject	TAM	Object	Verb	Oblique	Adjunct
(11)	Adama	ye	wari	da	Awa ma	kunu ¹
	Adama	PFV	money	give	Awa POSTP	yesterday

‘Yesterday, Adama gave (some) money to Awa.’

Furthermore, I find several aspect markers denoting habitual and the progressive aspect. Table 1 is an illustration of the most common markers and specifically, the most relevant for this thesis. Grammaticalization might have evolved the imperfective marker *be* from a locative copula *bε*,

	Marker	Meaning
Tense	ka	adjectival copula
	bε	locative copula
Aspect	be	habitual, progressive
	ká	subjunctive
	bena	future

Table 1: Tense-Aspect markers in Jula

which marks habitual aspect in Jula and progressive aspect in other Mande languages (Creissels 2020). Jula has few to no adjectives, whereby the majority of predicates are verbal or nominalized versions. See Table 2 for a reference to the most common adjectives (positives boldfaced) and their antonyms in Jula.

¹The original numbering in Kiemtoré (2022) is (4)

Adjective Pairs	
Positive/ Negative	Meaning
jan /surun	tall/long /short
bɔn /dɔgɔ	big /small
guli /fignɛ	heavy /light
kɔrɔ /dɔgɔ	old /young
gbɛle	expensive
teli	fast/speedy
gni	nice
dun	deep

Table 2: Most Common Adjectives in Jula

2 Theoretical Background

A common approach to the analysis of the underlying structure of comparatives is to assume that gradable predicates (i.e. adjectives) describe relations between individuals and degrees (Cresswell 1976). Degrees are abstract entities and denote parts in an ordering relation on a scale. von Stechow (1984) briefly discusses whether an account that eliminates degrees from an analysis of comparatives is fruitful, but comes to a negative conclusion. A possibility would be to assume that an adjective like 'tall' as in (12) is simply a relation between two individuals (Klein 1980). However, this assumption is hard to hold once the situation becomes more complex (13). A relation that simply exists between two individuals encounters problems as soon as anaphoric pronouns are part of the construction. Additionally, this kind of theory would have to assume strict nominal types for differentials and for measurements.

(12) *Mary is taller than Lou.*

(13) *Ede is taller than he is broad.*²

The delineation analysis is another option. On this account, there is an assumed partitioning of the dimension in that the comparee denotes a positive entailment of a predicate like 'tall', while the comparison standard holds the negated predicate 'not tall' (von Stechow 1984). A partitioning works well for languages that make use of a compositional strategy (14) to express comparatives, like Motu (Tip; Malayo-Polynesian) (Beck 2009).

(14) *'Mary is old and Tom is not old.'*

²Example from Stechow (1984). The original numbering is (xiii).

But this kind of analysis encounters problems in combination with differential measure phrases like *four years* as in (15) which is infelicitous. Compositional languages in fact don't have a necessity for degrees at all, since comparison can be made simply by stating that one object has a property while another does not.

(15) #*Mary is 4 years old and Tom is not old.*

Other accounts have redefined the measure-unit and called it 'portions' instead of 'degrees' (Francez & Koontz-Garboden 2017). Combinatory accounts take the philosophical notion of 'tropes' and separate states from degrees (Moltmann 2009). Even on a degree-based approach there are many different denotations. Degrees are generally taken to denote points on a scale, but there are accounts in favor of extents (Kennedy 2007a; 2007b), and accounts that define degrees not as points on a scale but as intervals (Seuren 1978; von Stechow 1984).

Although an analysis with degrees might not be the way to go for all languages, it seems to be the right way to analyze comparatives in Jula. The next subsections provide a general overview over the degree morphology, degree semantics, the syntax-semantics interface of comparatives and cross-linguistic variation in the analysis of exceed-comparatives.

2.1 Explicitness and Degree Comparison

What factors determine the variability that I find in comparative structures? Can the cross-linguistic differences in syntactic expression of comparatives be traced back to variation in the underlying semantics, or can I find universal parameters? Languages employ different strategies to encode comparison and crucially differ in whether they express the comparative relation morphosyntactically or grammatically. Under the explicit-implicit distinction, based on definitions from Kennedy (2007), languages are partitioned depending on whether they make use of dedicated morphology to encode comparison (16) or not (17).

(16) *Mary is taller than Lou.* explicit

(17) *Compared to Lou, Mary is tall.* implicit

Explicit comparison establishes an ordering relation between two individuals and the greater-than relation is grammaticalized, while the ordering in implicit comparison has to be inferred (Hohaus & Bochnak 2020). In other terms, I differentiate between whether comparison involves specialized morphology or if it takes advantage of the inherent context-sensitivity of the positive form.

For example, the English comparative operator *-er* or the periphrastic allomorph *more* is an example of specialized morphology. This pattern is common in the majority of Indo-European languages (Ultan 1972). German (18) and Spanish (19) exhibit the same structures.

- (18) *Anne is größer als Lisa.* — German —
 Anne COP bigger than Lisa.
 ‘Anne is bigger than Lisa.’
- (19) *Juan es más alto que Mario.* — Spanish —
 Juan COP more tall than Mario.
 ‘Juan is taller than Mario.’

Implicit comparison involves adjectives or gradable predicates in their positive form and establishes an ordering relation that is context-sensitive. In other words, the semantic function of compared to x is to manipulate the context relative to which the positive form is evaluated so that it only includes the argument of the adjective and the argument of *compared to*; the rest of the sentence constitutes an assertion that x is A in this revised context, while B is not A (Kennedy 2007a). This negative entailment pattern only arises in implicit comparison constructions. This is a non-trivial partitioning on the adjective’s domain (Kennedy 2007a), whereby both the positive and the negative extension cannot be empty. What does this mean? It entails that in an implicit comparative(17) Mary possesses the positive feature of the property, she is tall, while emphasizing the negative feature of Lou not possessing this property, Lou is not tall.

Not all languages draw such a clear division to determine explicit and implicit comparison. (In)Felicitous combination with differential measure phrases provides a crucial element to distinguish the two. Differential measure phrases may occupy the degree argument slot of an adjective. As soon as the degree argument slot is filled with a comparative operator or a measure phrase it renders implicitness void. Take (20) and (21) as an example:

- (20) *Mary is 4 feet taller than Lou.*
- (21) *# Mary is 4 feet tall compared to Lou.*

The latter example is nonsensical. I cannot meaningfully construct implicit comparison with a differential measure phrase. When I say *Mary is 4 feet tall*, the measure phrase denotes a measurement that binds the degree variable of the adjective, hence context-sensitivity is void.

Another distinction that can be drawn concerns the type of the comparison standard: specifically, whether the standard provides an individual or a degree. Kennedy (2007a) distinguishes between whether comparatives express orderings between arbitrary individuals (individual comparison), or if they (also) express orderings between individuals and arbitrary degrees, the value of which may be conveyed syntactically by complex degree descriptions. The individual/ degree distinction is important in that it conveys information not only about the possibility of abstraction in the language but also about the underlying semantics of the construction. A language that is only felicitous when comparing individuals to the exclusion of degrees and degree descriptions suggests the absence of degree semantics and possibly degrees in general.

2.2 Gradable Predicates and Scale Structure

Of equal importance is the type of the arguments and the way that comparative operators combine with them. A comparative establishes an ordering relation between two individuals, or an individual and a degree, making reference to a measurement scale, such as height (Hohaus & Bochnak 2020). This measurement scale or dimension is given by the gradable predicate and is usually an adjective. Gradability is not restricted to adjectives, but may also be expressed by gradable verbs, relational nouns, or adverbs. This results in several implications for the semantics of comparatives, but mostly it broadens the possibilities to express comparison.

The basic denotation of adjectives i.e. 'tall' and 'intelligent' orders the predicate on a spectrum (or a scale). Following an analysis in von Stechow (1984), these gradable adjectives are of type $\langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle$ and denote a functions from degrees to individuals (22) (Cresswell 1976, Seuren 1978, Rullmann 1995, inter alia). Adjectives are taken to be monotone in the sense of (23) (Heim 2001).

$$(22) \quad \llbracket \text{tall} \rrbracket = [\lambda d : d \in D_d. [\lambda x : x \in D_e. \text{tall}(x) \geq d]]$$

$$(23) \quad \text{A function } f \text{ of type } \langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle \text{ is monotone iff} \\ \forall x \forall d \forall d' [f(d)(x) = 1 \ \& \ d' < d \rightarrow f(d')(x) = 1]$$

The underlying structure of adjectives is rather abstract. It assigns adjectives a two-place mapping that is similar to the mapping of explicit comparatives (Klein 1980). Adjectives that do not employ degrees remain vague and are one-place predicates of type $\langle e, t \rangle$. Another way to analyze adjectives is to assume they denote measure functions directly from individuals to degrees (Kennedy 1999, 2007) with a denotation as in (24).

$$(24) \quad \llbracket \text{tall} \rrbracket = \lambda x. \text{HEIGHT}(x)$$

Gradable predicates predominantly come in antonym pairs of positive and negative counterparts and differ in the way they map to a scale. Some examples of antonym pairs are tall/ short and old/ young. Two main accounts exist in the literature: a degree-based view of antonymic pairs, where the negative counterpart is a decomposed form of the positive: little+adjective+er (Büring 2007), and an extent-based view which relies on antonyms sharing a scale (Kennedy 1997). Monotonicity principles, and behavior with too and enough can act as diagnostics to determine the polarity of an adjective (as in (24)) (Kennedy 1998; Meier 2003).

- (25)
- a Molly is tall enough to reach the top shelf. $\rightarrow \text{height}(M) \geq$ 'tallness' values necessary to reach shelf
 - b Molly is short enough to fit under the door. $\rightarrow \text{height}(M) \leq$ 'shortness' values necessary to fit
 - c positive+enough \geq lower bound of values $:::$ negative+enough \leq upper bound of values

Using these diagnostics for example, the adjectives *short* and *light* are indicated to be the negative antonyms of their respective antonym pairs while *tall* and *heavy* are the positives. This is indicated by the diagnostic in *c*. The combination of *tall* and *enough* accesses the lower bound of the values on a scale. What is measured are the degrees from 0 and up to the maximum degree of height that *Molly* has such that she can reach the top shelf. The same logic applies for *short enough* whereby the degrees are measured this time from the maximum degree of height that Molly has and above. Some adjectives like *warm* and *cold* do not have a clear cut zero threshold and often vary in different cultural contexts. These constitute conceptual antonyms. A definition for positive and negative antonyms is given in Rett (2007) as in (26).

- (26) For all adjectives A, A' and for all x in the domain of A, A',
 A and A' are antonyms iff: $\text{MAX}[A(x)] = \text{MAX}[A'(x)]$
 $\wedge A(x) \cap A'(x) = \text{MAX}(a(x))$,
 where MAX is defined relative to the direction of the scale

Adjectives modify the noun and denote properties of the objects they modify or represent. It is incremental to distinguish between two types of adjectives that differ in the type of standard they invoke; relative gradable adjectives and absolute gradable adjectives. Relative adjectives are adjectives like 'tall' and computed on the basis of the comparison class instantiated in a given context. The comparison standard or threshold is a context-dependent value on the underlying scale of measurement. Large and small make use of the same dimension and degrees, and impose reverse orderings. Absolute adjectives like *full* on the other hand have fixed, context-invariant standards, typically denoting the end-point of the measurement scale they encode. A different set of terms for these adjectives are minimum|maximum standard adjectives. *Bent* or *wet* are examples of such. They require a non-zero degree or a maximum-degree of the property for felicitousness. The negation of an absolute adjective entails the assertion of its antonym (Cruse 1986; Rotstein & Winter 2004).

The measure function analysis can be transported to gradable predicates that are not adjectives, although it is necessary to make some adjustments prior to being able to apply the measure function analysis to, for example, relational nouns. Complex nouns, which often are derived by nominalization - like *wisdom* from *wise* - are relational, they denote a property that somebody possesses; and the degree to which they possess this property can be measured. *Mary's wisdom* is an example. Nicholas (2004) defines two axioms that link the semantics of the adjective to the semantics of the nouns derived from it (27)-(28). Since I find many gradable predicates as nominalized properties in Jula, the axiomatic definition is relevant for the analysis to come.

- (27) Axiom 1: $\exists x. \text{wisdom}(x,m) \text{ iff } \exists d. d = \text{WISE}(m)$

- (28) Axiom 2: $\text{wisdom}(x,m) \rightarrow \mu(x) = \text{WISE}(m)$

The Measure Function μ associated with *wisdom* is the Measure Function associated with the adjective *wise*.

Applying this to *Mary’s wisdom*, I can apply axiom 2 and get a measure function μ of wisdom, that measures the degree to which Mary is wise ($\text{Mary} = m$). This assigns the same semantics to relational nouns as to the gradable adjectives the nouns are derived from. This distinction seems trivial at first, however is important in so far that comparison in Jula (as in many other non-Indo-European languages) involves complex nouns and nominalized arguments.

2.2.1 Evaluativity

Evaluativity presupposes that an individual possesses a gradable property that exceeds a contextually defined standard as in (28). The distribution of evaluativity (or norm-relatedness) is taken to be cross-linguistically universal in degree constructions like unmodified APs (Cresswell 1976; Stechow 1984; Kennedy 1999, 2007), equatives and interrogatives (Rett 2007, 2015).

(29) *Audu is tall.* \vdash Audu exceeds a contextual standard of tallness

Relative adjectives like ‘tall’/ ‘short’ require the standard to be contextually specified. The standard for Audu’s tallness in (29) is set by a standard which may vary depending on the context the phrase appears in. For example, it may be modified and situated in a context by adding the information in (30). For the unmodified AP, it suffices that Audu reaches a height of 1.80m to be considered tall in general. In a basketball player context, he will need to reach a height which is tall even for a basketball player in order for the sentence to be felicitous.

(30) *Audu is a tall basketball player.* \vdash Audu exceeds a contextual standard of tallness for a basketball player.

Two accounts exist in the literature that treat evaluativity as: **1) A covert operator** POS that resides in the head of the degree phrase and covertly binds the degree variable of the adjective (Stechow 1984; Kennedy 1999, 2007; Bartsch & Vennemann 1973); or **2) a degree modifier** EVAL, whose expression hinges on the polarity of the adjective and the polar-variance of the construction (Rett 2007; 2015).

On the first account POS is a null morpheme in unmodified APs that relates the adjective to a comparison class (31). POS and degree morphology (i.e. comparative morphemes, measure phrases) stand in complementary distribution as both bind the degree variable.

(31) $\llbracket pos \rrbracket = \lambda g \in D_{\langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle} . \lambda x \in D_{\langle e \rangle} . MAX\{d \mid g(d)(x)=1\} \geq \mathbf{std}(g)$ (Kennedy 2007)

The second account extends to all degree constructions. EVAL is systematic across gradable predicates and varies with the scale structure of the predicate and the polar-variancy of the quantifier (whether it entails its positive construction). EVAL is only expressed in equatives and interrogatives with the negative antonym (33). Economy principles and a markedness competition block the evaluative positive constructions in structures where semantic competition appears between mutually entailing objects (Rett 2007). Between the phrases in (32) and (33), the negative antonym is more marked than its positive counterpart. Hence, the non-evaluative

form of the construction with ‘short’ is blocked and only the non-evaluative form of the positive construction with ‘tall’ is available.

- (32) Musa is as tall as Audu. $\not\vdash$ Musa is tall
(33) Musa is as short as Audu. \vdash Musa is short

Rett (2007) showed that evaluativity is not restricted to only unmodified APs but can optionally appear in other constructions, its expression being contingent on the polarity of the adjective as well as the polar-variancy of the degree quantifier. Rett defines EVAL as a function from sets of degrees to the subset of degrees exceeding a standard s . s is a pragmatic variable unbound in the semantics denoting the contextual standard.

$$(34) \text{ EVAL}_i = \lambda D_{\langle d, t \rangle} \lambda d_{\langle d \rangle} . D(d) \wedge d > s_i \quad (\text{Rett 2007})$$

Cross-linguistically, comparatives cannot encode comparison. With relative adjectives, which require the standard to be contextually set, evaluativity is blocked in comparatives where the than-complement provides the comparison standard. The only condition under which comparatives become evaluative is if they are composed with lower-bounded adjectives like ‘dirty’ or extreme adjectives like ‘gorgeous’. These are naturally evaluative in that their standard just needs to exceed a zero-point of degrees (Kennedy & McNally 2005) or inherently feature a subset of degrees on a scale (Rett 2007). For example, in (35) *dirty* has a lower bound and exceeding a zero degree of dirtiness suffices to exceed the standard - giving rise to the evaluative entailment.

- (35) *This glass is dirtier than that one.* \vdash The glass is dirty.

There is another proposal by Kennedy (2007a) to determine the origin of evaluativity that deviates from the Stechow/Cresswell and Rett accounts and instead assumes a type-flexibility of the adjectives in a language. By positing a lexical type-shifting rule adjectives change from non-evaluative to evaluative types. Kennedy defines the rules as in (36).

$$(36) \text{ For any lexical item } A, \text{ if } \llbracket A \rrbracket \in D_{\langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle}, \text{ then there is a lexical item } A' \text{ such that: } \llbracket A' \rrbracket = \lambda x . \text{MAX} \{ d \mid \llbracket A \rrbracket (d)(x) = \succ \text{stnd}(\llbracket A \rrbracket) \}$$

I find that Jula APs encode evaluativity similarly to English adjectives, but it remains to be seen which of these accounts best describe the phenomenon in Jula.

2.3 The Syntax-semantics Interface of Comparatives

A distinction in formal research on comparatives is drawn between phrasal and clausal comparatives with regard to the type of the *than*-complement (the comparison standard) and whether it supplies an individual or a set. Two examples are given (37)-(38) to illustrate the difference.

(37) Mary is taller than [DP Lou]. PHRASAL

(38) Mary is taller than [CP Lou <is tall>]. CLAUSAL

Phrasal and clausal comparatives differ in their underlying semantics (Bhatt & Takahashi 2011; Heim 1985; Beck 2012; among others) and whether a comparative is phrasal or clausal hinges on the type of the comparison standard. Clausal comparatives denote a structure where a comparative operator compares two clauses. The *than*-complement supplies a clause-structure that derives a set of degrees, similar to the matrix clause. A comparative operator with a bi-clausal structure denotes a lexical entry as in (39).

(39) $[[\text{CLAUSAL}] = [\lambda D1 \in D_{\langle d, t \rangle}. [\lambda D2 \in D_{\langle d, t \rangle}. \text{MAX}(D2) > \text{MAX}(D1)]]]$
 such that there are two maximum degrees from sets of degrees of type $\langle d, t \rangle$ which are derived syntactically and the maximum of one set exceeds the maximum of another set.

Phrasal comparatives are more complex and can not be analyzed as straightforwardly as their clausal counterparts. Under a standard account, a phrasal comparative is represented with a lexical entry as in (40).

(40) $[[\text{PHRASAL}] = [\lambda x \in D_{\langle e \rangle} [\lambda P \in D_{\langle d(e, t) \rangle} [\lambda y \in D_{\langle e \rangle}. \text{max}(\lambda d. P(d)(y)) > \text{max}(\lambda d'. P(d')(x)]]]]]$
 where P stands for a property concept or a predicate over individuals and degrees.

Under this assumption, phrasal comparatives are mapped with a 3-place semantics and take a predicate over individuals and degrees alongside two individual-denoting DP's as arguments. Clausal comparatives take two sets of degrees as arguments, which have been locally derived in the syntax and deliver a maximum degree from each set. This compositional framework is defined in Heim (2001) and builds on the syntax from Bresnan (1973) and the semantics from von Stechow (1984).

2.3.1 The Direct-Analysis of Phrasal Comparatives vs. the Reduction Hypothesis

The analysis of phrasal comparatives has primarily followed two main approaches: A reduction analysis, based on reduced material in the form of ellipsis in the *than*-standard, and a direct analysis, where the *than*-standard feeds an individual into the derivation. Reduction Analyses seek to connect the *than*-phrase with a degree description denoting clause, considering it as part of a larger clausal constituent that has undergone reduction operations. In contrast, the Direct

Analysis proposes the interpretation of the than-phrase directly, necessitating the assumption of a new lexical entry for the degree operator. Under the Direct Analysis of phrasal comparatives, the degree operator directly combines with the individual-denoting DP-argument (Heim 2001). In cases where reduction operations are unavailable, a 3-place *-er* is forced (Bhatt & Takahashi 2007).

Under the reduction hypothesis the phrasal comparative has the underlying structure of (37) but the final surface structure of (37). This is the standard account for the English comparative operator *-er* (Lechner 2001; Merchant 2006; Pancheva 2007; inter alia). Several (covert) movement operations have taken place. The idea is this: *-er* quantifies over degrees and thereby has the properties of a quantifier (Heim 2001). Quantifiers undergo movement operations and scope out of their base position in order to be interpreted. Heim notes that degree operators behave similar to quantifiers and scope out of their base position in the degree phrase in order to be interpreted. This simultaneously resolves the antecedent containment (AC) problem, such that ellipsis may be licensed in the standard (Kennedy 1997). Ellipsis can only occur under the identity constraint - the gradable predicate in the matrix clause needs to be identical to the embedded clause. Under this account, the DegP-node is of type $\langle d, t \langle t \rangle \rangle$ a generalized quantifier over degrees, and undergoes Quantifier Raising in order to resolve a type mismatch. Movement of a silent *wh*-pronoun from the than-clause out of the degree argument position of the (elided) gradable predicate derives another set of degrees. The comparative operator gets a type $\langle \langle d, t \rangle \langle d, t \langle t \rangle \rangle \rangle$. Under the reduction hypothesis *-er* is mapped with a 2-place semantics that takes degree predicates as its arguments.

(41) $\llbracket \text{-er} \llbracket \text{than} \llbracket \text{OP } \lambda d_1. \llbracket \text{Bill is } d_1\text{-tall} \rrbracket \rrbracket \llbracket \lambda d_2. \llbracket \text{John is } d_2\text{-tall} \rrbracket \rrbracket \rrbracket$
 EXAMPLE FROM BHATT & TAKAHASHI (2007)

(42) a. Mary ran faster than _{wh} John did run _t fast.
 b. $\llbracket \text{-er} \llbracket \text{than} \llbracket \text{wh} \llbracket \text{John did run } t \text{ fast} \rrbracket \rrbracket \rrbracket \llbracket \text{Mary ran } t \text{ fast} \rrbracket \rrbracket$
 EXAMPLE FROM HEIM (2001)

Under the Direct Analysis, no silent structure is posited. The than-phrase, usually consisting of a DP is interpreted directly and the operator takes three arguments. The phrasal 3-place operator has received several lexical entries, each discussed at length in Beck (2012). All entries differ in their assumption of how the operator combines with its arguments and which arguments enter the derivation first. The accounts can be divided into an operator à la Heim (1985) and an operator à la Kennedy (1997). The third is likewise a 3-place operator but describes comparison with a degree.

- 1 $\llbracket \text{-er}_{(Kennedy)} \rrbracket = \lambda \text{Adj}_{\langle d \langle e, t \rangle \rangle} \cdot \lambda y_{\langle e \rangle} \cdot \lambda x_{\langle e \rangle} \cdot \text{MAX}(\lambda d, \text{Adj}(d)(x)) > \text{MAX}(\lambda d, \text{Adj}(d)(y))$
- 2 $\llbracket \text{-er}_{(Heim)} \rrbracket = \lambda y_{\langle e \rangle} \cdot \lambda \text{Adj}_{\langle d \langle e, t \rangle \rangle} \cdot \lambda x_{\langle e \rangle} \cdot \text{MAX}(\lambda d. \text{Adj}(d)(x)) > \text{MAX}(\lambda d. \text{Adj}(d)(y))$
- 3 $\llbracket \text{-er}_{(degree)} \rrbracket = \lambda \text{Adj}_{\langle d \langle e, t \rangle \rangle} \cdot \lambda d_{\langle d \rangle} \cdot \lambda x_{\langle e \rangle} \cdot \text{MAX}(\lambda d. \text{Adj}(d)(x)) > d$

The main difference between 1. and 2. is in fact visible at Logical Form (LF). The comparative operator in Heim’s phrasal comparative forms a constituent with the *than*-phrase which moves (at LF) between the subject position and no unit directly denoting taller (or similar) is created. On Kennedy’s account, the structure presupposes no movement and most importantly, is not ambiguous. Although all approaches derive the same truth conditions, the operators differ substantially, in their derivation at LF and it is disputable which entry might be the correct one.

2.4 Background on Implicit Analyses

There is a surprising lack of analytical material for implicit comparative constructions. The standard frameworks dealing with comparatives make do with defining either a context or leaving a free contextual variable that is unbound in the semantics. However, one account formulates an analysis for implicit comparatives (Hohaus 2015). This account hinges on defining a parameter frame that restricts the available context with situation semantics. I will adopt this framework and apply it to the analysis of the implicit comparative in Julia.

Let’s examine the two incremental points from Hohaus (2015) that constrain the context in implicit comparatives:

SITUATION: A situation describes a part of a possible world, where a world is a maximal situation such that it is not a proper part of any other situation. As a part-whole construct, the following generalization may hold: If a situation s is part of a world w and another situation s' is part of a world w , then $s \oplus s'$ (the mereological sum) is also part of w .

FRAME: A frame restricts the domain to which a predicate can apply to a spatial, temporal, or individual framework (Maienborn 2001). A proposition holds true in that domain, but there exist no conditions for the truth of that proposition outside of this domain. In this regard, a frame adds a domain restriction to the set of situations that a sentence denotes. Frame setters restrict the domain of definition of a function from situations to truth values. The requirement that these situations be minimal with respect to the content of the frame then severely restricts which value assignments are still available for the free context variable. The frame that restricts a set of situations $\langle s, t \rangle$ to a subset of these situations $p(s)/q(s)$.

Depending on the position of the frame setter, the restriction is added to a different set of situations, which is reflected in the interpretation (Hohaus 2015). Applying this framework to the definition for implicit comparison mentioned in 2.1, I get a restriction for the free contextual variable c that is set by the frame and may be analyzed with regard to the situations it modifies.

I illustrate the application of such a framework example (Hohaus 2015):

(43) *Compared to Peter, Mary is older.*

In the case of (43) restrict the situations to situations that are a comparison with Peter. The **FRAME** thus imposes a setting on the *compared to* expression that yields (positive) truth conditions only in the case where comparison is with Peter. Possible situations may be represented

as tuples. For the denotation of the frame for Mary, I get a set of situations that specify the dimension age (44).

(44)

<i>Mary is older...</i>	
<i>s1</i>	$\langle \textit{Mary}, \textit{Peter}, \text{AGE} \rangle$
<i>s2</i>	$\langle \textit{Mary}, \textit{Brandon}, \text{AGE} \rangle$
<i>s3</i>	$\langle \textit{Mary}, \textit{Hossan}, \text{AGE} \rangle$
...	...

From these situations, where the contextual parameter is defined to being compared to Peter, the situations are restricted to situation where Mary is compared in a specific dimension of *age* to Peter. This leaves the only possible situation that contains Mary and Peter and they are compared along a dimension of age.

(45)

... compared to Peter.	
<i>s1</i>	$\langle \textit{Mary}, \textit{Peter}, \text{AGE} \rangle$
<i>s2</i>	$\langle \textit{Mary}, \textit{Peter}, \text{HEIGHT} \rangle$
<i>s3</i>	$\langle \textit{Cory}, \textit{Peter}, \text{WEIGHT} \rangle$
...	...

The extension for FRAME is given in (46). It means that a domain restriction (p/q) applies to a set of situations to yield a subset of these situations.

$$(46) \quad \llbracket \text{FRAME} \rrbracket = \lambda p_{\langle s,t \rangle} . \lambda q_{\langle s,t \rangle} . \lambda s_{\langle s \rangle} : (p)(s) . q(s)$$

$$(47) \quad \llbracket \textit{Compared to Peter}, \gamma \textit{ Mary is older} \rrbracket_g \\ = \lambda s : \exists x_{\langle e \rangle} . \exists \mu_{\langle s, \langle e, d \rangle \rangle} [\mu(s)(x) \geq \mu(s)(\textit{Peter})], \text{MAX}(\lambda d . \text{age}(s)(\textit{Mary}) \geq d) > g(7, d)$$

This yields the only permissible value for the free degree variable in a contextual comparative, in this case Peter's age (47) which is specified by a function g that assigns a value (degree) to a context (compared to Peter). The following truth conditions hold: The maximum degree of Mary's age exceeds the defined contextual standard (in this case Peter's age).

3 Cross-linguistic Variation and Analyses

Several theories discuss the underlying structure of comparatives and how it might be semantically analyzed. A comparative account of comparatives is given by von Stechow (1984) and highlights accounts by Cresswell, Klein, Lewis, Hellan, among others, scrutinizing how they fare with problems that arise for example with Russel's ambiguity under a Russelian account, while proposing improvements to the respective accounts so they may adequately deal with such problems. In other work, Stassen (1985) has presented a typological study of different comparatives in different languages and coined the term exceed-comparatives. Since then, several accounts have dealt with the analysis of exceed-languages. I will investigate relevant literature in the following sections.

3.1 Parametric Classification of Comparatives

A crucial aspect where languages diverge is in the semantic nature of gradable expressions themselves. Beck et al. (2009), through crosslinguistic analysis, suggest that languages can exhibit differences in whether their gradable predicates incorporate degree arguments, represented as arguments of type $\langle d \rangle$. In languages with degree semantics, gradable predicates are characterized as $\langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle$. Conversely, in languages without degree semantics, gradable predicates are vague and of type $\langle e, t \rangle$.

Beck et al (2009) hinge their classification of comparatives cross-linguistically on the presence or absence of syntactic and semantic parameters, repeated in (i)-(iii).

(i) Degree abstraction parameter (DAP): A language's ability to have a binding of degree variables in the syntax.

(ii) Degree Semantics Parameter (DSP): A language does|does not have gradable predicates (type $\langle d \rangle$ and related), i.e. lexical items that introduce degree arguments.

(iii) Degree Phrase Parameter (DegPP): A language does|does not have overt degree phrases. The degree argument position of a gradable predicate may/ may not be overtly filled. This parameter arises only for languages with a +DAP setting, because this position is filled by expressions that trigger a binding of the degree argument.

These semantic macro-parameters are proposed as a classification of languages that employ different strategies for expressing the comparative as opposed to the majority of European languages. The first two parameters are semantic, while the latter is only syntactic in nature, but governs the occurrence of degree phrases in overt syntax. Any language that has comparison constructions that envelop differential comparatives and comparison with a degree is a [+DSP] language. They are [-DSP] if the language does not make any reference to degrees in their grammar, and for example, makes use of conjunction strategies to refer to a scale. An example of a conjunctive language is Motu (Papuan Tip; Papua New Guinea) that expresses comparison emphasizing the

negative antonym in the standard (48).

- (48) *Mary na lata, to Frank na kwadoḡi.*
Mary TOP tall, but Frank TOP short
'Mary is taller than Frank.'³
(Example from Beck et al. 2009)

Languages with a positive DAP-setting allow for subcomparatives, degree questions, measure phrases and give rise to Negative Island effects (NIE). These languages allow the formation of sets of degrees through predicate abstraction over degree variables. A language that has a negative setting of the [DAP] parameter lacks the possibility for degree operators to bind degree variables, or interact in scope operations. On an account where degree quantifiers and wh-particle movement derive sets of degrees and degrees, additional scope bearing units like modals or MPs in the construction give rise to scope ambiguities. Degree operators that take wide scope need a binding of degree variables. Using constructions with scope ambiguities as in (52) may indicate whether a language has degree abstraction and a degree phrase.

- (49) SCOPE AMBIGUITIES (The draft is 10 pages long. . .)
a. The paper is required to be exactly 5 pages longer than that.
(i) Reading 1: The paper must be 15 pages (no longer, no shorter).
(ii) Reading 2: The paper must be at least 15 pages long (but it could be longer).

Using these diagnostics in the paper Beck et al. (2009) show that for example, languages like Mandarin Chinese and Yoruba (Benue-Congo, Nigeria) fall into the class of languages with a [+DSP], [-DAP] parameter setting, since they don't show degree abstraction and hence lack scope interaction, MPs and DegQs.

3.2 The Case of Yoruba and Tswefap with a Degree Abstraction Parameter

Howell (2013) argues that Yoruba requires bound variables of type $\langle d \rangle$ (a +DAP setting) to explain facts relating to degree relatives and degree questions. These findings differ from those of Beck et al. (2009) who claim, primarily on the basis of data from scope ambiguities in the comparative, that Yoruba, or exceed-comparatives in general, have a -DAP setting. The alternative account proposed by Howell hinges on differences in the semantics of differential measure phrases in Yoruba and English instead of a distinction by parameters to explain the lack of scope ambiguities.

- (50) *Ade sanra ju baba re lo.*
Ade be.fat exceed father his STD
'Ade is fatter than his father.'

GRADABLE VERB

³The original numbering in Beck (2009) is (2).

- (51) *Ade je omo sisanra ju baba re lo.*
 Ade be child fat exceed father his STD
 ‘Ade is a fatter child than his father.’⁴

GRADABLE ADJECTIVE

This underscores the non-trivial role played by the type of the gradable predicate and scope bearing units like differential measure phrases in comparative constructions. Howell suggests that this observation is at the heart of the apparent lack of scope ambiguity in Yoruba, namely, because there is evidence that Yoruba measure phrases do not have the semantic type of degree quantifiers. Empirical investigation of differential measure phrases revealed that measure phrases with modified numerals (e.g. exactly x , at least x , approximately x) seem to be unavailable, in fact better explained if measure phrases denote degrees or sets of degrees directly (von Stechow 1984). In languages which lack modified numeral MPs, then, there is no clear indication that measure phrases have a quantificational meaning (Howell 2013). In such a case, measure phrases are not scope bearing units and cannot quantify over degrees as part of a degree argument. Hence, for wide and narrow scope, degree phrases at Logical Form (LF) generate the same truth conditions.

In addition to scope ambiguities, less-comparatives are another indicator of degree abstraction in a language (??). In comparatives, modals and measure phrases act as degree quantifiers. However, in Yoruba Howell (2013) argues that MPs are not degree quantifiers but instead behave like nominals and therefore, in *less*-comparatives in Yoruba two distinct readings are never generated.

- (52) *The paper is required to be less long than that.*

A similar phenomenon occurs in Tswefap (Clem 2019) which exhibits patterns likewise suggesting a negative setting for the Degree Abstraction Parameter. However, despite similar constraints, Tswefap shows different features that license gradability, mainly positing that gradability comes about by verbal predicates like *be.tall* as in (53). The paper argues for a distinction between gradable verbs and gradable adjectives in Tswefap based on the diagnostics proposed by Beck et al. (2009). It demonstrates that gradable verbs in Tswefap possess degree arguments, whereas gradable adjectives, lacking any acceptable degree morphology, are best treated as vague $\langle e, t \rangle$ predicates. This suggests a syntactic category-based divide in Tswefap regarding the semantic type of gradable predicates, highlighting the possibility for certain predicates to be of type $\langle e, t \rangle$ even in languages allowing abstraction over degrees.

Only gradable verbs may combine with degree operators like ‘very’. Interestingly, no other degree operators than ‘very’ can co-occur with attributive adjectives in Tswefap. This suggests that attributive adjectives in Tswefap behave differently from gradable verbs, indicating that adjectives do not take degree arguments, but verbs do.

- (53) *Chimi a seh tey.*
 Chimi FACT be.tall very.
 ‘Chimi is very tall.’

⁴Examples from Howell 2013.

- (54) *Chimi a yoh 'ta sesege (*tey) mbaga.*
 Chimi FACT see one tall very man
 ‘Chimi saw a (*very) tall man.’⁵

Bochnak (2018) makes a similar observation for Washo. Gradable predicates cannot appear in environments requiring an analysis as $\langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle$ predicates. Consequently, in line with the data from Tswefap, without evidence supporting the necessity of degree arguments for gradable predicates, the simplest analysis treats attributive adjectives as vague $\langle e, t \rangle$ predicates.

3.3 The Syntax-Semantics Mapping of Luganda Exceed-Comparatives

Hausa, Tswefap, and Yoruba (in general exceed-comparatives) are arguably phrasal, resulting from the restriction of nouns or individual-denoting arguments in the than-complement (the object of ‘exceed’). This has led to assumptions in the literature matching exceed-comparatives with a 3-place semantics and a direct analysis (Heim 1985, 2001; Howell 2013; Zimmermann 2008). I will review one account that proposes that the respective exceeds may de facto have both a 2-place and a 3-place analysis.

Luganda exceed-comparatives pattern very similar to other exceed-comparatives (Bochnak 2018). I find subordinated infinitive comparatives, and nominalized argument-types. Bochnak provides data from Luganda exceed-comparatives that can convincingly be fit with a 2-place as well as a 3-place distinction. Cross-linguistically, this questions the strict syntax-semantic mapping of exceed-comparatives.

The argument put forth by Bochnak (2018) is the following: Applying both 3-place and 2-place analyses to the phrasal comparatives in Luganda yields the same truth conditions. I provide examples from the paper to illustrate.⁶

- (55) *Kizito asinga Kato obukulu.*
 Kizito a-singa Kato o-bu-kulo
 Kizito NC1-old AUG-NC15-exceed Kato
 ‘Kizito is old exceeding Kato.’
 (Example from Bochnak)⁷

The differences between the 3-place and 2-place analysis in Bochnak hinges on the semantics of the nominalizing particle *-bu* and whether it is semantically vacuous, as nominalizing particles are assumed to be under a standard semantic account (Heim & Kratzer 1998). Starting with the common analysis of phrasal comparatives being 3-place operators and by using the tools for English phrasal 3-place analysis, the correct truth conditions are derived intuitively (56). This additionally relies on the assumption that the adjective in Luganda has the same underlying

⁵Examples from Clem 2019.

⁶The lexical entries for phrasal and clausal operators were given in (40) and (39)

⁷The original numbering in Bochnak (2018) is (19).

semantics as adjectives in English have, namely a relation between individuals and degrees of type $\langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle$ (Cresswell 1976; Heim 2001; Kennedy & McNally 2005).

$$(56) \quad \llbracket S \rrbracket = 1 \text{ iff } \max(\lambda d. \text{old}(Kizito) \geq d) > \max(\lambda d'. \text{old}(Kato) \geq d)$$

However, assuming that *-bu* in fact contributes to the semantics by reversing the order of the arguments of gradable adjectives instead of assuming that nominalized adjectives are inherently relational and also of type $\langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle$ (Nicholas 2004), the result is a derivation where the nominalized adjectives shift to a type $\langle e, \langle d, t \rangle \rangle$. The predicate now expects an individual as its first argument. Consequently, two sets of degrees are derived which are exactly the arguments a 2-place operator expects, resulting in (57).

$$(57) \quad \llbracket S \rrbracket = 1 \text{ iff } \text{MAX}(\lambda d. \text{age}(Kizito) \geq d) > \max(\lambda d'. \text{age}(Kato) \geq d)$$

By integrating the semantic contribution of nominalizing particles and possession phrases with the measure function analysis, the result is a convincing argument for the availability of a 2-place analysis for phrasal comparatives in Luganda. Furthermore, it supports the intuition that has also been put forward for Yoruba (Howell 2013) and Tswefap (Clem 2019), namely that the underlying semantics for comparative operators is not rigid and de facto influenced by the type of the predicates it combines with.

4 Explicit Comparison

With the literary basics in place, let's take a closer look at the comparative constructions in Jula that were introduced in the first section. I start by describing the general structure based on the diagnostics for phrasal/ clausal and explicit/ implicit distinctions and continue by investigating the distribution and syntax to establish a first picture of the underlying semantics.

4.1 Syntax and Distribution

The comparative operator is denoted by the lexical verb *teme* 'surpass' which is intransitive. Postpositions introduce the oblique argument and assign oblique case in intransitive structures. *TEME* comes in two variants; embedded as an infinitive version of surpass headed by a matrix predicate, or bare, often preceded by a habitual marker. The bare construction is restricted to nominalized arguments that form complex nouns, often as part of a possessive phrase, and to measurements (Measure Phrases or MPs) like '2 meters', or individuals. The other explicit operator *dan* is a full predicate and appears in a main verb construction, adhering to the natural SOV word order.

The two constructions differ in the kind of arguments they take. The following sections will take an in-depth look at the syntax and distribution of each of the explicit comparative constructions.

4.1.1 The Infinitival Adjective Construction

The adjectival predicative exceed-construction is a combination of an adjectival matrix predicate, consisting of a copula and an adjective, with an infinitive form of *exceed*. Similar to Spanish *estar* and *ser*, Jula copulas express different notions of being, in this case distinguishing between an attributive copula *ka* with the notion of ‘being’ and a locative copula *bε* with the notion of ‘having’. Both copulas exclusively appear in constructions with adjectival predicates as (58)(59) illustrate.

(58) *Fofana ka dɔgɔ.*
 Fofana COP small
 ‘Fofana is small.’

(59) *N bε fanga.*
 1PN.SG COP strength
 ‘I am strong.’
 (Lit.) ‘I have strength.’

In the comparative postposition *kan* introduces the second (semantic) argument, and assigns oblique case. The infinitive construction licenses adjectival or adverbial predicates, and the type of the copula differs with regard to the predicates. Predicative comparatives in Jula show the following patterns: The adjectival matrix predicate comes with both versions of the copula and both can be used in comparative constructions with an infinitive version of exceed. Both copulas appear in these structures as the matrix predicate, whereby ‘exceed’ is followed by the comparison standard, an oblique object introduced by the postposition *kan*.

(60) *Fofana ka guli ka tɛmɛ Kofi*
 Fofana COP heavy INF surpass Kofi
kan.
 POSTP
 ‘Fofana weighs more than Kofi.’
 (Lit.) ‘Fofana is heavy surpassing Kofi.’

(61) *Yirikurun-w blanin bε sanfɛ tɛmɛ*
 Log-PL put COP high surpass
karitonin-w kan.
 box-PL POSTP
 ‘The logs are stacked higher than the boxes.’
 (Lit.) ‘The logs are stacked high surpassing the boxes.’

Taking (60) as a starting point, the syntax that emerges may be represented as in (62). The adjectival predicate consists of *Fofana ka guli*, whereby the infinitive exceed is a subordinated construction that is part of the AP. The infinitive *ka* heads a finite phrase FinP. An oblique syntactic argument is adjoined as a prepositional phrase to the internal argument position of the verb. Kiemtoré (2022) provides evidence for the presence of an unpronounced pronoun (pro-drop) in Jula infinitival constructions; a feature that can generally be found in infinitive constructions (Landau 2001). This topic will be further explored in the analysis section; for now it suffices to say that the pronoun moves out of the specifier position of the VP and to the specifier of the IP in the subordinate clause, where it becomes covert.

(62)

This structure is rigid. Movement tests have shown that the infinitival phrase cannot be moved as a whole (it may not be fronted), otherwise the phrase is ungrammatical. It is possible to front the oblique object only, however, at the cost of sacrificing the structure of the phrase. (63) shows that I need additional material in order to move constituents. It also shows that the postposition adds substantially to the structure of comparison, denoting a sense similar to the English ‘than’.

- (63) *Musa ka jan, nga Adu ka jan ka tɛmɛ.*
 Musa COP tall, but Adu COP tall INF surpass.
 ‘Musa is tall, but Adu is taller.’
 (Lit.) ‘Musa is tall, but Adu is tall surpassing (Musa).’

4.1.2 The Infinitival Adverbial Construction:

Ka tɛmɛ is not restricted to being subordinated by an adjectival matrix predicate but may also appear headed by an adverbial construction as in (64) and (65).

- (64) *Gninan-w be boli (joonan) ka tɛmɛ jakumani kan.*
Mice-PL HAB run (faster) INF surpass cat POSTP.
'The mice run faster than the cat.'
(Lit.) 'The mice run (fast) to surpass the cat.'

- (65) *Lulu be gitari fɔ gnanaman ka tɛmɛ Hawa kan.*
Lulu HAB guitar play beautiful INF surpass Hawa POSTP.
'Lulu plays the guitar more beautifully than Hawa.'
(Lit.) 'Lulu plays the guitar beautifully to surpass Hawa.'

I take (64) to provide a syntactic tree for the adverbial construction. The differences to the adjectival construction are minimal, centering around a difference in the matrix predicate in which the adverbial may consist of a verb and an often implicit adverb. The habitual marks the constituent boundary of the subject and is followed by a verb. It is possible to omit the low manner adverb in (65) and still elicit the same meaning.

(66)

The dimension which is supplied directly by the adjective in an adjectival predicate comes from the adverb and verb combination in the adverbial case. The implicit adverb leaves the dimension of the phrase implicit as well. The adverb that supplies the degree is implicit in (64), while overtly spelled out in (65). Under the assumption that most verbs that can be modified by adverbs have a degree variable as part of their meaning, the default dimension for a verb like ‘run’ is for example, speed, when situated in a greater-than ordering. For verbs that don’t directly invoke a dimension along a temporal or spatial dimension, the degree of quality or degree of skill is what is being compared. To express a dimension different to the default, the adverb has to be overtly expressed, as in ‘beautiful’. Further discussion around the adverbial dimension will be given in 4.2.2.

4.1.3 The Bare Exceed-Construction

The other construction with *tɛmɛ* is bare. It takes two semantic arguments that are nominalized, often part of a complex noun in a (covert) possessive phrase as in (67). In fact the construction is restricted to nominalized arguments, the constituent boundary is indicated by the habitual marker and the comparison standard is either a complex noun or a degree description.

- (67) *Fofana jan-ya be tɛmɛ 1.80m kan.*
 Fofana tall-NOM HAB surpass 1.80m POSTP
 ‘Fofana is taller than 1.80m.’
 (Lit.) ‘Fofana’s height surpasses 1.80m.’

(68)

The dimension is supplied directly by the nominalized argument (see the axiomatic definition in the background section 2.2). The nominalized property, for example ‘height’ in (67), is derived via a measure function and stands in a possessive relation with the subject *Fofana*. More on the semantic analysis will be given in the formal analysis section 4.3.

4.1.4 The Main Verb Exceed-Construction

The second explicit comparative construction in Jula is a main verb construction consisting of the main verb *dan*. *Dan* licenses nominalized arguments and degree descriptions. It is a full predicate with two NP-arguments adhering to the SOV-word order in Jula. (69) illustrates the comparative.

- (69) *Fofana jan-ya be 1.80m dan.*
 Fofana tall-NOM HAB 1.80m **surpass**.
 ‘Fofana is taller than 1.80m.’
 (Lit.) ‘Fofana height surpasses 1.80m.’

Similarly, in this construction the dimension comes from the nominalized property that stands in a possessive relation with subject (and object respectively). This is also a case of nominal ellipsis in the standard. (70) illustrates this phenomenon. The arguments in (70) are two complex NP's marked by the possessives *ka* and *ta* respectively. These two markers constitute a possessive pair and instigate that the elided noun in the comparison standard stands in a relation to the noun in the subject possessive phrase (painting). Since the nominalized properties are identical in the standard and its antecedent, the identical material is elided.

- (70) *Anna ka jadilan be Mary ta dan.*
 Anna POSS painting HAB Mary POSS surpass
 'Anna paints better than Mary.'
 (Lit.) 'Anna's painting surpasses Mary's.'

I take the example from (70) to provide a syntactic tree for the second explicit construction in Jula.

(71)

4.2 Towards a Compositional Analysis of Explicit Comparison in Jula

With the syntactic analysis in place, I can move forward to the semantics of the explicit constructions and integrate the information with the goal to provide a formal compositional analysis. As a repetition, these are the three central claims in this thesis:

- 1 Jula comparatives are phrasal, but have a 2-place semantics, contrary to common assumptions regarding the syntax-semantics mapping of phrasal and clausal comparatives.
- 2 Jula adjectives behave similar to English adjectives, encoding a positive operator in the their denotation, which may also serve as a diagnostic for true adjective-hood.
- 3 The explicit comparative construction can felicitously combine with the negative antonym of adjective pairs, establishing a greater-than relation with an antonym. This is possibly the result of blocking effects and syntactic restraints.

I repeat these claims from the introduction to provide a guiding structure throughout the following sections, starting with the first claim regarding the syntax-semantics mapping of the comparative operators *teme* and *dan*. I start by investigating whether or not Jula has degree semantics and degree abstraction in 4.2.1. Section 4.2.2 solidifies this claim by providing more evidence from the adverbial construction and highlights an interesting feature of implicitness that emerges in these constructions. It seems that verbs that can be modified by low manner adverbs in Jula have a slot for dimensions as part of their lexical meaning, which may be accessed by ‘exceed’.

Section 4.2.3 will investigate how evaluativity is attested for in negative as well as positive antonym constructions, whilst highlighting the properties that make it possible for Jula comparatives to establish a greater-than relation with negative antonyms. Building on this, I make a case for claim 2 and 3 in this thesis.

4.2.1 Determining Degree Semantics and Degree Abstraction in Jula

Beck et al. (2009) cluster comparatives into different classes based on macro parameters. Although I don’t apply the parametric approach for classification, the diagnostics are useful to determine some basic facts about whether or not a language has proper degree semantics and comparatives that make use of degrees. The parameters are repeated in (72).

- (72)
- a Degree abstraction parameter (DAP): A language’s ability to have a binding of degree variables in the syntax.
 - b Degree Semantics Parameter (DSP): A language does|does not have gradable predicates (type $\langle d \rangle$ and related), i.e. lexical items that introduce degree arguments.
 - c Degree Phrase Parameter (DegPP): A language does|does not have overt degree phrases. The degree argument position of a gradable predicate may|may not be overtly filled. This parameter arises only for languages with a +DAP setting, because this position is filled by expressions that trigger a binding of the degree argument.

These parameters have been used to classify languages that do not give rise to the usual comparative strategies. A language has degree semantics and makes use of gradable predicates of i.e. type $\langle d \rangle$ and $\langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle$ (DSP) if it has comparison with a degree and differential comparatives. If a language exhibits scope ambiguities and Negative Island Effects (NIE) it additionally has the ability to abstract over degrees. Subcomparatives, degree questions and direct measure phrases are indicators of a degree phrase.

Exceed-type languages have been classified with a [+DSP][-DAP] setting under a parametric approach. However, following a discussion for Yoruba (see discussion in section 3.1 and 3.2 for more details), Howell argued that Yoruba, despite showing no scope ambiguities, has the ability to bind degree variables in the syntax. Howell (2013) provides an argument whereby Yoruba requires bound variable of type $\langle d \rangle$ in order to explain facts that relate to degree relatives and degree questions. She proposes an alternative account which rests on differences in the semantics

of differential measure phrases in Yoruba and English and hinges on the type of predicates that Yoruba exceed-comparatives can combine with. Following Howell (2013), I identify similarities in Jula, which does not show scope ambiguities, but nonetheless shows degree abstraction.

The availability of differential comparatives (73) - (74) and comparison with a degree (75) show that Jula has degree semantics, as it can compose directly with measure phrases. It has been pointed out that these expressions denote degrees or sets of degrees directly (Stechow 1984).

- (73) *Mina ka dɔgɔ ka tɛmɛ Hawa kan san loru ma*
 Mina COP small INF surpass Hawa POSTP year five POSTP
 ‘Mina is five years younger than Hawa.’
 (Lit.) ‘Mina is small surpassing Hawa by five years.’ DIFFERENTIAL COMPARATIVE
- (74) *Musa ka jan ka tɛmɛ Audu kan santimɛtɛrɛ 30 ma.*
 Musa COP tall INF surpass Audu POSTP centimeter 30 POSTP
 ‘Musa is 30 cm taller than Audu’ DIFFERENTIAL COMPARATIVE
- (75) *Fofana ka jan ka tɛmɛ 1.80m kan.*
 Fofana COP tall INF surpass 1.80m POSTP
 ‘Fofana is taller than 1.80m.’
 (Lit.) ‘Fofana is tall surpassing 1.80m.’ DEGREE COMPARISON

Syntactically, the differential degree argument is an adjunct and adjoined to the prepositional phrase that holds the comparison standard (76).

(76)

Moving on to the other diagnostics of degree abstraction and the availability of a degree phrase, scope ambiguities and negative island effects can only be shown if a language also allows a degree phrase. Conversely, only if a language allows degree abstraction does it have a degree phrase and the possibility to express subcomparatives, degree questions and measure phrases. I find that subcomparatives and degree questions are available in Jula as (77)-(80) show respectively.

(77) *Kofi hakimima-ya be di?*
 Kofi smart-NOM COP how
 ‘How intelligent is Kofi?’

Degree Question

(78) *Minabilaminan bon-ya be di?*
 Closet big-NOM COP how
 ‘How big is the closet?’

Degree Question

Note however, that (77) and (78) show that Jula allows for degree questions, but that the arguments are nominalized properties in possessive relations with their objects. Nominalized

properties don't prove the presence of a degree phrase (and degree abstraction) as the argument simply denotes a DP. The degree is locally derived in the subject constituent.

- (79) *Tabali jan-ya be tɛmɛ a ɔsurun kan.*
 Table tall-NOM HAB surpass 3SG width POSTP
 'The table is longer than it is wide.'
 (Lit.) 'The table's height surpasses its width.'

Subcomparative

- (80) *Minabilaminan ka jan ka tɛmɛ da ɔsurun kan.*
 Shelf COP tall INF surpass door width POSTP
 'The shelf is higher than the door is wide.'
 (Lit.) 'The shelf's height surpasses the width of the door.'

Subcomparative

Subcomparatives show the same restriction. De facto, these are not bi-clausal structures but a case of nominal subcomparatives. In (79), both constituents are nominal arguments. On a standard account, the DegP is a generalized quantifier over degrees, which undergoes quantifier raising (QR) in order to resolve a type mismatch (Heim 2001). Quantifying over degrees as well as movement of a silent *wh*-pronoun allows for the derivation of two sets of degrees in subcomparatives, which are subsequently being compared. I can generalize here that the comparison standard in Jula is restricted to nominal constituents - a feature that is also licensed by postpositions (Bhatt & Takahashi 2011). The phrase that is headed by *kan* is therefore structurally similar to (phrasal) *than*-complements in English and I take it as an indication of the phrasal nature of Jula comparatives with the intransitive *exceed*. However, what is also striking in comparison with other *exceed*-strategy languages like Yoruba is that Jula does not seem to exhibit *wh*-movement and *wh*-elements (question words) stay in-situ (in the base position where they are generated).

Turning to scope ambiguities, Howell's assumption hinges on measure phrases in Yoruba having a different underlying semantics, namely not employing degree quantifiers. Scope ambiguities arise in comparatives when other scope bearing units are present such as modals or measure phrases. Under the assumption that measure phrases instead denote sets of degrees or just degrees, no distinct truth conditions are generated in phrases where one expects to see scope ambiguities (Howell 2013). Assuming that Howell's account of the semantics of measure phrases is on track, this could also explain the absence of scope ambiguities in Jula, additionally to the non-quantificational nature of the lexical verb.

Under a quantificational approach, I should get two different readings with different truth conditions for ambiguous cases as in (81).

- (81) 'John thinks the yacht is longer than it is.'

The consequence of such an ambiguity is that two simultaneous beliefs are generated - a consistent and an inconsistent belief, which both generate different truth conditions that arise depending on

whether the *than*-clause is interpreted de re or de dicto (Stechow 1984). A de dicto interpretation of the *than*-clause is only possible when the DegP falls within the scope of the relevant intensional verb, while a de re interpretation allows for both wide and narrow DegP scope (Heim 2001). Looking at similar cases that elicit ambiguities, I find that in Jula the structure is such that it only allows one reading, and different truth conditions are never generated. See (82) and (83) for illustration.

- (82) *Hawa jan-ya tɛmɛ-na n miiri-ya kan.*
 Hawa tall-NOM surpass-PFV 1SG think-NOM POSTP
 ‘I thought Hawa was taller.’
 (Lit.) ‘Hawa’s tallness surpassed my thinking.’

- (83) *N hakili la gafe tun ka jan ni nin ye*
 1SG memory POSTP book PAST COP long CONJ DEM POSTP.
 ‘The book is longer than I remember.’
 (Lit.) ‘In my memory the book is longer than this.’

Less-comparatives would paint an even clearer picture for cases where quantification and scope create ambiguities. But similar to Yoruba, Jula does not permit less-comparatives, instead constructing the phrase with negation (84).

- (84) *Ama ma jan ka tɛmɛ a dogocɛ kan.*
 Ama NEG.COP tall INF surpass 3SG small.brother POSTP
 ‘Ama is less tall than her brother.’
 (Lit.) ‘Ama is not taller than her younger brother.’

The intransitive constructions in Jula with *tɛmɛ* and the postposition *kan* is phrasal. And with the foundation in place that the comparative operator and other scope bearing units like measure phrases do not move and quantify over the degree argument of the adjective or adverb in Jula, I can show that degree abstraction takes place elsewhere.

Tɛmɛ abstracts over the degree variable of the argument in the comparison standard, whose dimension is pragmatically resolved. See (84) for illustration. The matrix predicate consisting of an individual and an adjective phrase is not identical to the comparison standard which only permits nominal constituents (so at most nouns that are part of possessive phrases), and is therefore not subject to ellipsis. Hence, the reduction hypothesis is not an option (section 2.3.1). The dimension however, is given by the adjective ‘tall’ and has to be pragmatically resolved in the comparison standard, which is fed into the derivation as a first argument as a degree variable. Kiemtoré (2022) argues in his dissertation on Jula complementation that infinitive constructions in Jula likewise employ a covert pronoun (see section 4.1 for a syntactic structure). I claim the covert pronoun is of type $\langle d \rangle$ and subject to partial control from the matrix predicate (Landau 2001). It is fed into the derivation as a degree variable and abstracted over at the boundary of the infinitive phrase. The logical form of the infinitive phrase looks as in (85). I receive a type $\langle d, t \rangle$ at the boundary of the infinitive phrase, a function from degrees to truth values.

‘...ka tɛmɛ Audu kan.’

(85)

4.2.2 Adverbial Modification and the Implicit Dimension

Let’s look at another construction with the infinitive version of ‘exceed’ that supports the semantics for the infinitive comparative I have proposed in the previous section. The implicitness of the dimension shows that there is a certain amount of covert structure in the infinitive comparative construction in Jula. For a verb as like ‘run’ or ‘drive’ the dimension by default concerns speed, hence the adverb *joona* may be implicit (86). ‘Further’ or ‘longer’ do not exist as adverbs in Jula and would require contextual specification to elicit this meaning.

(86) *Hawa be boli ka tɛmɛ Lulu kan.*
 Hawa HAB run INF surpass Lulu POSTP
 ‘Hawa runs faster than Lulu.’

For all comparison that concerns situations where actions like ‘writing’ or ‘painting’ are described, actions that don’t necessary favour a spatial or temporal dimension, the skill of performing this action is what is compared. This comparison of skill is usually expressed by the low manner adverb ‘well’ *gnanaman* as in (87) and (88).

(87) *Fofana be gitari fo gnanaman ka tɛmɛ Hawa kan.*
 Fofana HAB guitar play well INF surpass Hawa on
 ‘She plays the guitar better than Hawa.’
 (Lit.) ‘She plays the guitar well surpassing Hawa.’

- (88) *Gninan-w be boli ka tɛmɛ jakumani kan.*
 Mouse-PL HAB run INF surpass cat POSTP.
 ‘The mice run faster than the cat.’

The analysis of the adverb ‘well’, and by extension adverbs in general in Jula hinges on the account of Kennedy and McNally (1999, 2005) who discuss the conditions under which participles can be modified by ‘well’. They note that participles must meet certain semantic criteria to allow modification by ‘well’: they must for example denote gradable properties. Closed-scale participles, like ‘well loaded’, can be modified by proportional degree modifiers such as ‘partially’ or ‘fully’. However, participles associated with open scales, like ‘worried’, do not permit such modification. The possibility of a degree reading with ‘well’ is determined by the participle’s standard of comparison, which cannot be the maximum value on the scale. This understanding leads to a hypothesis that a degree reading of ‘well’ is generally available but neutralized when the standard of comparison is a maximum value. Kennedy & McNally (2005) observe a connection between degree modifiers and the type of the scale of the adjective they combine with. Certain modifiers impose restrictions on the kind of gradable predicates they modify. ‘Well’ as a degree modifier (89) and ‘well’ as an adverb (90) license closed-scale adjectives. The meaning comes from measuring the ‘goodness’ of an event, which underlies ‘well’, related to the degree to which a subject possesses the property. The output is a new gradable predicate meaning based on the relative adjective ‘good’.

- (89) I acquainted Beck well with the facts.

- (90) Beck is someone well acquainted with the facts.

The semantics of ‘well’ are based on its function as a measure function on events. This interpretation aligns with a Davidsonian semantics for manner adverbs, where all gradable manner adverbs, including ‘well’, denote measure functions on events. The denotation of the adverb ‘well’ is seen as similar to the adjective ‘good’, mapping an event onto a scale of goodness. However, ‘well’ does not specify the standard for what counts as good; this information is provided contextually by the event. Treating the semantics of adverbs this way will ensue that all gradable manner adverbs denote measure functions on events.

When the adverb combines with participles or the verb denoting the property or skill, it imposes an implicit condition that an event argument must be available for the measure function to operate on. Modification via Selective Binding corresponds to a manner/quality reading, where the event is evaluated based on aspects like neatness, rapidity, or skill. (Kennedy & McNally 2005).

Under the approach of Kennedy & McNally, the analysis suggests that the argument of the adverb must possess some degree of the corresponding adjectival property, in this case ‘well’. This indicates that the subject has participated in the event described by the verb to some

extent of ‘goodness’. Following the intuitions from Kennedy & McNally and assuming a Davidsonian event approach to adverbial semantics, I posit the following sample lexical entry for adverbial predicates (88) that treats the adverb as denoting a measure function of an event.

$$(91) \quad \llbracket \text{Audu runs fast} \rrbracket = \lambda e . \text{Audu runs in } e \wedge \text{speed}(e) \geq d$$

4.2.3 Antonymy, Negation and Scale Structure

The previous sections have given some insight into what the general semantics of explicit comparative constructions in Jula look like. I take two other factors under scrutiny, which are researched cross-linguistically and are crucial for determining underlying structures, namely, antonymy and negation. Comparatives in general encode a greater-than relation between two entities (or sets of entities). But it is felicitous to say ‘*Bill is shorter than Bob.*’ without any problems regarding the combination of a relation that measures from 0 and up and the negative part of an antonym pair. Verbal operators like ‘exceed’ seem to embody this notion even more strongly. I follow (Kennedy 1997, 2007; Sassoon 2010, 2015; inter alia) in assuming that relative adjectives that constitute true antonym pairs like ‘tall/short’ share a scale and that in the case of measurement with a negative antonym, the direction of the scale is reversed.

$$(92) \quad 0 \longrightarrow \text{Audu}'\text{sheight} \qquad \text{TALL}$$

$$(93) \quad \text{Musa}'\text{sheight} \longleftarrow \infty \qquad \text{SHORT}$$

The comparative operator *temε* felicitously combines with negative antonyms as in (94) and (95). I take ‘short’ and ‘light’ to be the negative parts of the adjective pairs ‘tall|short’ and ‘heavy|light’, using the diagnostics described in section 2.2.

(94) *Musa ka dɔgɔ ka temε Audu kan.*
 Musa COP short INF surpass Audu POSTP
 ‘Musa is shorter than Audu.’
 (Lit.) ‘Musa is short surpassing Audu.’

(95) *Sakɔsi ka fignε ka temε walisi kan.*
 The bag COP light INF surpass the suitcase POSTP
 ‘The bag is lighter than the suitcase.’

The same patterns hold true under negation. (94) may be negated (96) just as the positive antonym construction may be negated (101).

(96) *Musa ma dɔgɔ ka temε Audu kan.*
 Musa COP tall INF **surpass** Audu POSTP
 ‘Musa is not shorter than Audu’
 (Lit.) ‘Musa is short not surpassing Audu.’

- (97) *Musa ma jan ka tɛmɛ Audu kan.*
 Musa NEG.COP tall INF surpass Audu POSTP
 ‘Musa is not taller than Audu’
 (Lit.) ‘Musa is tall not surpassing Audu.’

(98)

The syntactic structure for the negative antonym case is given in (98). Negation in Jula only comes about by negating the respective TAM-markers. An overview of the negative counterparts of TAM-markers is given in ??⁸. Negation particles or morphemes do not exist by themselves in the language, hence, in order to negate a proposition, the respective counterparts of the tense-mood-aspect markers have to be inserted. A common feature of many Mande-languages is the availability of commutation of negation (Creissels 1997). This entails that the language’s limited availability of expressing negated concepts or propositions has the consequence that negation travels in the syntactic structure. Negation may target a specific verb in a phrase, but in fact only be expressed syntactically higher, if that is where a TAM-marker is posited. I find that this holds for Jula comparative constructions. The negation in (95) and (101) targets ‘exceed’, but

⁸This is an excerpt from the original table. A full version can be found in A.Kiémtores dissertation *Issues in Jula Complementation*.

since the landing site for the negation close to ‘exceed’ is in the I-head, it has no means of being spelled out. It continues to the copula *ka* higher in the syntax. The result is the negated version *ma*. Explicitly, negating an affirmative sentence consists in replacing a positive TAM-marker with the corresponding negative form (Kíémtoire 2022).

Forms		Functional Domains
Positive	Negative	
bε	tε	Existential/ locative copula
ka	ma/ man	Predicative/ adjectival copula
Affirmative	Negative	
be	te	Imperfective - habitualis

Table 3: Positive and negated TAM-amrkers

In (96) Musa is still required to be short or required to be tall respectively. Under the assumption that the restrictions to the expression of negation are of a morphosyntactic nature, the expression of ‘Musa is not tall’ in the context of a comparative is in fact blocked. In order to elicit this reading, it is necessary to turn to the polar opposite of the adjective. This pattern gives rise to the following equivalence relation:

(99) Not tall = Short

4.2.4 Evaluativity

Turning to the last point (and last claim) regarding the semantics of Jula comparatives, I find that adjectives in Jula are in fact, similar to English adjectives and encode evaluativity. Native speaker judgments for different contexts have determined that a contextual threshold needs to be met as in (100). This feature disappears in comparative construction. The reason for the lack of evaluativity in comparatives is the cross-linguistically universal assumption that the positive morpheme (or evaluative marker) stands in complementary distribution with any comparative morphology. The degree argument of an (adjective) may be filled either by comparative morphemes or the positive (covert) operator binding the degree variable (Kennedy 2007).

Native speaker judgments for (100) is infelicitous if Audu does not exceed a contextual threshold of tallness. In a context where Audu reaches a height of 1.50m, native speakers opted for a different construction to express ‘*Audu is tall.*’, one not involving a predicative construction and the predicative copula.

(100) <i>Audu ka jan.</i> Audu COP tall. ‘Audu is tall.’	(a) CONTEXT 1: NO CONTEXTUAL TALLNESS Audu is 1.50m tall. # Infelicitous
--	--

(b) CONTEXT 2: CONTEXTUAL TALLNESS ✓Felicitous
 Audu is 1.80m tall.

Evaluativity can be found in all adjectival predicate constructions in Jula. The pattern persists for adjectival phrases that involve the negative polar antonym of the relative adjective pair. In contrast to many other African languages that derive gradable predicates from verbs, evaluativity may be used as a diagnostic for determining "true" adjectives.

- | | |
|--|---|
| <p>(101) <i>Musa ka dɔgɔ.</i>
 Musa COP short.
 ‘Musa is short.’</p> | <p>(a) CONTEXT 1: NO CONTEXTUAL SHORTNESS
 Musa is 1.70m.
 # Infelicitous</p> <p>(b) CONTEXT 2: CONTEXTUAL SHORTNESS
 Musa is 1.50m.
 ✓Felicitous</p> |
|--|---|

4.3 Formal Analysis

Section 4.2 has provided some simple examples of the comparative construction that are found in Jula. I have seen that Jula uses two verbs to express explicit comparison, both denoting the sense of *surpass*. *Tɛmɛ* is intransitive and appears in a copular or adverbial infinitive construction or appears bare. *Dan* appears in a main verb structure adhering to the Jula word order. Section 4.2 started investigating the underlying semantics of comparatives in Jula, based on the theoretical background that was provided in section 2. I use this background to motivate the 2-place analysis for the two explicit verbal operators *tɛmɛ* and *dan* in this section. A short summary is provided at the end of the section.

Starting with the infinitive construction, I take (5) as an example, repeated in (102), to provide the first formal analysis for the adjectival construction.

- (102) *Hawa ka kɔrɔ ka tɛmɛ Mina kan.*
 Hawa COP old INF surpass Mina POSTP.
 ‘Hawa is older than Mina.’
 (Lit.) ‘Hawa is old surpassing Mina.’

At Logical Form (LF) the representation of the infinitive phrase FinP looks as in (103). As I have shown in previous sections, the exceed-comparative in Jula is phrasal and the standard is restricted to nominal arguments - the type licensed by postpositions. Hence, I assume that the dimension that is in the standard of comparison and pragmatically resolved is a nominalized property of type $\langle e, d \rangle$. Brackets $<$ and $>$ indicate silent material.

(103) ...ka tɛmɛ Mina kan.

(104) Hawa ka kɔrɔ...

(102) is a compositional representation of (105) (For reference to the syntax of the adjectival predicative constructions, see section 4.1). Following standard accounts, I take adjectives in Jula to relate individuals and degrees, denoting a property of type $\langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle$. Additionally, I assume along with Bochnak (2018) that nominalization morphemes are non-vacuous and change the type of the nominalized property from $\langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle$ to $\langle e, d \rangle$ providing a maximal degree. Nominalization in Jula is realized by suffixing the particle *-ya* to the adjective. The nominalized adjective is now part of a possessive phrase relating to an individual or object. Applying the axioms described in Nicholas (2004), every noun (or nominalized property) has as part of its meaning a measure function μ such that the measure function associated with the nominal argument is the same measure function that is associated with the adjective it is derived from (like *wisdom* and *wise*). Since a noun like *wisdom* or *age* in the case of (102) is inherently relational, I take the possessive relation to just denote the identity function $\lambda R. R$ (Barker 2002).

(105)

(105) is an illustration of the compositional derivation for (102), taking the syntactic surface structure into consideration. The adjective which is of type $\langle d \langle e, t \rangle \rangle$ combines with the FinP (the infinitive phrase) via predicate restriction, a compositional operation RESTRICT (Chung & Ladusaw 2001). The operation modifies the two degree-arguments (since both the FinP and the predicate expect a degree as their first argument) and yields a predicate over individuals and degrees. By using predicate restriction it is possible to saturate an argument later in the derivation. ‘Exceed’ here takes two degree-arguments: The first argument is the degree of Minas age that comes from deriving the maximal degree directly from the nominalized property and possessee Mina. The second degree is supplied by the covert pro pronoun, which denotes a degree variable. Pro-drop is a feature of infinitive phrases and Jula infinitives show parallel structures (Kiemtoré 2022). This $\langle \text{pro} \rangle$ degree variable is subject to partial control from its antecedent (Landau 2001). At the edge of the infinitive phrase, the degree variable is once again abstracted over (also a semantic feature of infinitives), leaving a function from degrees to truth values that continues in the derivation to compose with the matrix predicate. (106) describes the individual steps.

- (106)
- i $\llbracket \text{Mina} \langle \text{age} \rangle \text{kan} \rrbracket = \text{AGE}(\text{Mina})$
 - ii $\llbracket \text{t}\bar{\text{e}}\text{m}\bar{\text{e}} \rrbracket = \lambda d'. \lambda d. d > d'$
 - iii $\llbracket \text{t}\bar{\text{e}}\text{m}\bar{\text{e}} \text{kan} \rrbracket (\llbracket \text{Minakan} \rrbracket) = [\lambda d'. \lambda d. d > d'](\text{AGE}(\text{Mina}))$
 - iv $\llbracket \langle \text{PRO} \rangle \text{t}\bar{\text{e}}\text{m}\bar{\text{e}} \text{Mina kan} \rrbracket = d > (\text{AGE}(\text{Mina}))$
 - v $\llbracket \text{IP} \rrbracket = 1$ iff $d > \text{AGE}(\text{Mina})$
 - vi $\llbracket \text{ka t}\bar{\text{e}}\text{m}\bar{\text{e}} \text{Mina kan} \rrbracket = \lambda d. d > \text{AGE}(\text{Mina})$
 - vii $\text{RESTRICT}(\llbracket \text{k}\bar{\text{o}}\text{r}\bar{\text{o}} \rrbracket, \llbracket \text{FinP} \rrbracket) = \lambda d. \lambda x. \text{old}(x) \geq d \wedge d > \text{AGE}(\text{Mina})$

- viii $EC(\llbracket k\acute{o}r\acute{o} \textit{ ka } t\acute{e}m\acute{e} \textit{ Mina kan } \rrbracket) = \lambda x.\exists d.old(x) \geq d \wedge d > AGE(Mina)$
- ix $\llbracket k\acute{o}r\acute{o} \textit{ ka } t\acute{e}m\acute{e} \textit{ Mina kan } \rrbracket(\llbracket Hawa \rrbracket) = [\lambda x.\exists d.old(x) \geq d \wedge d > AGE(Mina)](Hawa)$
- x $\llbracket Hawa \textit{ ka } k\acute{o}r\acute{o} \textit{ ka } t\acute{e}m\acute{e} \textit{ Mina kan } \rrbracket = \exists d.old(Hawa) \geq d \wedge d > AGE(Mina)$
- xi = 1 iff there is a degree to which Hawa is old that exceeds the degree of Mina's age.

Turning to the adverbial version of the infinitive construction, the derivation is more complex. Again, I will illustrate by providing a derivation of (107).

Adverbial *ka tēmē*:

- (107) *Hawa be boli ka tēmē Lulu kan.*
 Fofana HAB run INF **surpass** Lulu POSTP.
 ‘Hawa runs faster than Lulu.’
 (Lit.) ‘Hawa runs surpassing Lulu.’

Note that the dimension in this example is implicit. As discussed in section 4.2.2 the verb ‘run’ encodes as part of its meaning a degree slot, which may be accessed by ‘exceed’ and specified by an adverb. All verbs which may be modified by adverbs incorporate a dimension as part of their meaning in Jula. By default, the dimension for ‘run’ accessed by ‘exceed’ is one of speed. The adverb ‘fast’ measures the degrees of speed in that situation and relates the degree of speed to the (running) event. The situation itself is denoted as an event variable $\langle v \rangle$ and follows standard event semantics rules. *Boli* is an intransitive verb, and hence, of type $\langle v, t \rangle$. (108) illustrates the logical form of the adverbial predicate. The derivation of the infinitive construction follows a similar pattern as its adjectival counterpart, differing only in that age has been substituted by speed. The node where the infinitive phrase feeds into the derivation is indicated with the FinP. Unpronounced material is indicated with $\langle \rangle$.

- (108) *Hawa be boli <joona> ka tēmē Lulu kan.*

- (109)
- i $\llbracket Lulu \langle teliya \rangle kan \rrbracket = \text{SPEED}(Lulu)$
 - ii $\llbracket \text{teme} \rrbracket = \lambda d'. \lambda d. d > d'$
 - iii $\llbracket \text{teme } Lulu \text{ kan} \rrbracket = \lambda d. d > \text{SPEED}(Lulu)$
 - iv $\llbracket \langle \text{PRO} \rangle \text{ teme } Lulu \text{ kan} \rrbracket = d > \text{SPEED}(Lulu)$
 - v $\llbracket \text{IP} \rrbracket = 1$ iff $d > \text{SPEED}(Lulu)$
 - vi $\llbracket ka \text{ teme } Lulu \text{ kan} \rrbracket = \lambda d. d > \text{SPEED}(Lulu)$
 - vii $\llbracket \langle joona \rangle \rrbracket = \lambda e. \text{SPEED}(e)$
 - viii $\llbracket boli \rrbracket = \lambda e. \lambda d. \lambda x. x \text{ runs } d - \text{fast in } e$
 - ix $\text{RESTRICT}(\llbracket boli \rrbracket, \llbracket \langle joona \rangle \rrbracket) = \lambda e. \lambda d. \lambda x. x \text{ runs } d - \text{fast in } e \wedge \text{SPEED}(e)$
 - x $\text{EC}(\llbracket boli \langle joona \rangle \rrbracket) = \lambda d. \lambda x. \exists e. x \text{ runs } d - \text{fast in } e \wedge \text{SPEED}(e)$
 - xi $\text{RESTRICT}(\llbracket boli \text{ joona} \rrbracket, \llbracket \text{FinP} \rrbracket) = \lambda e. \lambda d. \lambda x. (x \text{ runs } d - \text{fast in } e \wedge \text{SPEED}(e)) \wedge (d > \text{SPEED}(Lulu))$
 - xii $\text{EC}(\llbracket boli \langle joona \rangle ka \text{ teme } Lulu \text{ kan} \rrbracket) = \lambda e. \lambda x. \exists d. (x \text{ runs } d - \text{fast in } e \wedge \text{SPEED}(e)) \wedge (d > \text{SPEED}(Lulu))$
 - xiii $\llbracket boli \langle joona \rangle ka \text{ teme } Lulu \text{ kan} \rrbracket = [x \text{ runs } d - \text{fast in } e \wedge \text{SPEED}(e) \wedge d > \text{SPEED}(Lulu)](Hawa)$
 - xiv = 1 iff there is an event and there is a degree of speed such that Hawa runs d -fast in e and that degree exceeds the degree of speed that Lulu has.

If this analysis for the infinitive exceed-construction is on track, I can tentatively posit the following lexical entry for *teme* as in (110).

$$(110) \quad \llbracket t\epsilon m\epsilon \rrbracket = \lambda d'.\lambda d.d' > d$$

Comparison with a Degree

The next construction is the comparison with a degree, one of the most eminent proofs for a language having degree semantics. The measure phrase in the comparison standard *1.80m* is a degree description and supplies a degree of type $\langle d \rangle$ directly.

- (111) *Audu jan-ya be tεmε 1.80m kan.*
 Audu tall-NMLZ HAB surpass 1.80m POSTP.
 ‘Audu is taller than 1.80m.’
 (Lit.) ‘Audu’s height surpasses 1.80m.’

(112)

The derivation for (111) is provided below. The first degree is the measure phrase (i). The second degree is supplied by the subject phrase consisting of a nominalized property in a possessive relation (vii). The comparative operator takes both degrees and compares them (viii).

- (113) i $\llbracket 1,80m \text{ kan} \rrbracket = \lambda d.d = 1.80m$
 ii $\llbracket t\epsilon m\epsilon \rrbracket(\llbracket 1,80m \rrbracket) = [\lambda d'.\lambda d.d > d'](1,80m)$
 iii $\llbracket t\epsilon m\epsilon 1.80m \text{ kan} \rrbracket = \lambda d.d > 1,80m$
 iv $\llbracket jan \rrbracket = \lambda d.\lambda x.tall(x) \geq d$
 v $\llbracket ya \rrbracket = \lambda P_{\langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle}.\lambda x.\{d | \text{MAX}(P(x)) \geq d\} = \lambda x.P(x)$
 vi $\llbracket janya \rrbracket = \lambda x.HEIGHT(x)$
 vii $\llbracket janya \rrbracket(\llbracket Audu \rrbracket) = [\lambda x.HEIGHT(x)](Audu)$
 viii $\llbracket be t\epsilon m\epsilon 1.80m \text{ kan} \rrbracket(\llbracket Audu janya \rrbracket) = [\lambda d.d > 1,80m](HEIGHT(Audu))$
 ix = 1 iff the maximum degree of height that Audu has exceeds 1.80m.

The Differential case

Another case that needs to be looked at is the case with a differential comparative. I take the example from section 4.2.1, as in (73), repeated in (114). Implicitly, an unspecified differential degree is universally present in comparatives. In a general comparative expression as ‘*Musa is taller than Audu*’ the differential degree is existentially quantified over, but numerically unspecified. In a differential comparative, this degree is spelled out and the vague degree is replaced by the measurement. Under this assumption, the verbal comparative ‘exceed’ takes three degree arguments and the third differential degree is omitted for economic reasons in regular derivations.

- (114) *Musa ka jan ka tɛmɛ Audu kan santimɛtɛrɛ 30 ma.*
Musa COP tall INF surpass Audu POSTP centimeter 30 POSTP
‘Musa is 30cm taller than Audu.’
(Lit.) ‘Musa is tall surpassing Audu by 30 cm.’

The standard method to handle differential comparatives, (that is a comparative that measures the distance between two objects on a measurement scale) is to assume an interval system instead of points of degrees (Stechow 2008). The degrees are concatenated by an operation of sequencing and addition. This means that a scale of height consists of units of height measurements (like cm) which are sequenced such that $d = 1\text{cm}$. The additive scale now returns a degree of 30 cm is equivalent to $30[\text{cm}]_{\text{height}}$. A measure phrase like 1.80m or 2m can on this account saturate the degree argument of a gradable predicate by referring to that specific point in the sequence. In this way, I can describe the differential measurement between two individuals like Musa and Audu in (114) as a measure of units (degrees). I follow von Stechow (2008) and assume that the measure phrase composes with the comparative operator and describes a relation of distance between two degrees (step iii). (115) is the structure tree of (114).

(115)

- (116)
- i $\llbracket \text{Audu kan} \rrbracket = \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu})$
 - ii $\llbracket \text{santimeterε 30 ma} \rrbracket = \lambda d. d = 30 \text{ cm}$
 - iii $\llbracket \text{tεmε} \rrbracket = \lambda d''. \lambda d'. \lambda d. d > d'' \wedge \text{DISTANCE}(d, d'') = d'$
 - iv $\llbracket \text{tεmε} \rrbracket (\llbracket \text{Audu kan} \rrbracket) = [\lambda d''. \lambda d'. \lambda d. d > d'' \wedge \text{DISTANCE}(d, d'') = d'] (\text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu}))$
 - v $\llbracket \text{tεmε Audu kan} \rrbracket (\llbracket 30 \text{ cm} \rrbracket) =$
 $[\lambda d. d > \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu}) \wedge \text{DISTANCE}(d, \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu})) = d'] (30 \text{ cm})$
 - vi $\llbracket \langle \text{pro} \rangle \text{tεmε Audu kan 30cm ma} \rrbracket =$
 $d > \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu}) \wedge (\text{DISTANCE}(d, \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu})) = 30 \text{ cm})$
 - vii $\llbracket \text{ka IP} \rrbracket = \lambda d. d > \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu}) \wedge (\text{DISTANCE}(d, \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu})) = 30 \text{ cm})$
 - viii $\text{RESTRICT}(\llbracket \text{FinP} \rrbracket), (\llbracket \text{jan} \rrbracket) =$
 $\lambda d. \lambda x. (\text{tall}(x) \geq d) \wedge (d > \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu}) \wedge \text{DISTANCE}(d, \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu})) = 30 \text{ cm})$
 - ix $\text{EC}(\llbracket \text{jan FinP} \rrbracket) =$
 $\lambda x. \exists d. (\text{tall}(x) \geq d) \wedge (d > \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu}) \wedge \text{DISTANCE}(d, \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu})) = 30 \text{ cm})$
 - x $\llbracket \text{ka jan FinP} \rrbracket (\llbracket \text{Musa} \rrbracket) =$
 $[\lambda x. \exists d. (\text{tall}(x) \geq d) \wedge (d > \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu}) \wedge \text{DISTANCE}(d, \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu})) = 30 \text{ cm})] (\text{Musa})$
 - xi $\llbracket \text{Musa ka jan ka tεmε Audu kan santimeterε 30 ma} \rrbracket =$
 $\exists d. (\text{tall}(\text{Musa}) \geq d) \wedge (d > \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu}) \wedge \text{DISTANCE}(d, \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu})) = 30 \text{ cm})$
 - xii = 1 iff there is a degree such that Musa is tall to this degree and this degree exceeds Audu's degree of height by 30cm.

The Main verb construction

Dan is a full predicate and main verb construction whose arguments likewise are restricted to complex nouns, comprised of individuals and nominalized properties headed by a possessive phrase, or consisting of degree descriptions directly (117).

- (117) *Fofana ka jadilan be Anna ta dan.*
 Fofana POSS painting HAB Anna POSS **surpass**.
 ‘Fofana paints more beautifully than Anna.’
 (Lit.) ‘Fofana’s painting surpasses Anna’s.’

(118)

The structure tree for (117) is provided in (118) and a step-by-step derivation in (119). *Dan* is of type $\langle d, \langle d, t \rangle \rangle$, the same type as *temε*. I treat possessives in Jula like semantic genitive structures that at their head-complex have a type $\langle \langle e, t \rangle \langle e \rangle \rangle$, similar to determiners (Hartmann & Zimmermann 2001). The genitive phrase combines with the predicate *painting* which is of type $\langle e, t \rangle$ and yields an individual painting of type $\langle e \rangle$. The *iota*-operator denotes uniqueness and is indicated in the meaning of the possessive relation in step (i). The same operation is done for the possessive phrase in the object argument *Anna ta* which additionally contains the elided noun *painting* and the dimension which is pragmatically resolved, but supplies a measure function from individuals to degrees. Composing the measure function of *beautiful* with the unique beautiful painting (of Fofana/ Anna) derived in the possessive phrases, the result is a degree *d* (v, viii). *Dan* takes both degrees as arguments and compares them (x-xii).

- (119)
- i $\llbracket ka \rrbracket = \lambda y. \lambda P. \iota x [P(x) \wedge R(x, y)]$
 - ii $\llbracket ka \text{ jadilan} \rrbracket = \iota x [\text{painting}'(x) \wedge R(x, y)]$
 - iii $\llbracket Fofana \text{ ka jadilan} \rrbracket = \iota x [\text{painting}'(x) \wedge R(x, Fofana')]$
 - iv $\llbracket beautiful \rrbracket = \lambda x. \text{BEAUTY}(x)$
 - v $\llbracket Fofana \text{ ka jadilan} \langle \text{gnanama} \rangle \rrbracket = \text{BEAUTY}(Fofana' \text{ s painting})$
 - vi $\llbracket ta \rrbracket = \lambda y. \lambda P. \iota x [P(x) \wedge R(x, y)]$
 - vii $\llbracket Anna \text{ ta} \langle \text{jadilan} \rangle \rrbracket = \iota x [\text{painting}(x) \wedge R(x, Anna')]$
 - viii $\llbracket Anna \text{ ta} \langle \text{jadilan} \text{ gnanama} \rangle \rrbracket = \text{BEAUTY}(Anna' \text{ s painting})$
 - ix $\llbracket dan \rrbracket = \lambda d'. \lambda d. d > d'$
 - x $\llbracket dan \rrbracket (\llbracket Anna \text{ ta} \rrbracket) = [\lambda d'. \lambda d. d > d'] (\text{BEAUTY}(Anna' \text{ s painting}))$
 - xi $\llbracket Anna \text{ ta} \text{ dan} \rrbracket (\llbracket Fofana \text{ ka jadilan} \rrbracket)$
 $= [\lambda d. d > \text{BEAUTY}(Anna' \text{ s painting})] (\text{BEAUTY}(Fofana' \text{ s painting}))$
 - xii $\llbracket Fofana \text{ ka jadilan} \text{ Anna} \text{ ta} \text{ dan} \rrbracket = \text{BEAUTY}(Fofana' \text{ s painting}) > \text{BEAUTY}(Anna' \text{ s painting})$
 - xiii = 1 iff Fofana's d -beautiful painting surpasses Anna's d -beautiful painting.

The main verb construction can also take degree descriptions as an argument. This complies with the notion of modified measure phrases that are nominal arguments and denote a degree type $\langle d \rangle$ directly, instead of a set of degrees. The derivation for (120) thus follows a similar pattern as in (119), with the exception that *depth* as a nominalized property directly supplies a measure function DEPTH and is inherently relational. I therefore take the possessive relation to denote the identity function (Barker 2002). The measure function takes an individual as its argument and results in a maximum degree (Kennedy 2007a)

- (120) *Ji dun-ya be 2m dan.*
 Water deep-NMLZ HAB 2m **surpass**.
 'The water is deeper than 2m.'
 (Lit.) 'The water's depth surpasses 2m.'

(121)

- (122)
- i $\llbracket dan \rrbracket = \lambda d'. \lambda d. d > d'$
 - ii $\llbracket 2m \rrbracket = \lambda d. d = 2m$
 - iii $\llbracket 2m dan \rrbracket = \lambda d. d > 2m$
 - iv $\llbracket dun \rrbracket = \lambda d. \lambda x. deep(x) \geq d$
 - v $\llbracket ya \rrbracket = \lambda P_{\langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle}. \lambda x. \{d \mid \text{MAX}(P(x)) \geq d\} = P(x)$
 - vi $\llbracket dunya \rrbracket = \lambda x. \text{DEPTH}(x)$
 - vii $\llbracket ji dunya \rrbracket = \text{DEPTH}(water)$
 - viii $\llbracket Ji dunya 2m dan \rrbracket = \text{DEPTH}(water) > 2m$
 - ix = 1 iff the degree of depth of the water exceeds a depth of 2m.

Dun denotes the adjective *deep* which relates individuals and degrees (Cresswell 1976). The nominalization function takes a predicate and an entity x and returns the maximum degree of that entity of that property measured on a scale (v). In step (vi) the entity *ji* 'water' is fed into the derivation for x and comes into the derivation as the second degree and consequently, second argument of the comparative operator *dan*. This yields the truth conditions in (ix).

Antonyms and Negation

In this part I consider the cases of comparatives that involve negative antonyms and negation. The semantic analysis of EXCEED in combination with a negative antonym (i.e. *tall*) follows a similar pattern as its positive counterpart. On an extent-based view, where relative adjectives like *tall/short* share a scale, the degrees measured in '*Musa is shorter than Audu*' are measured from infinity to Musa's maximal degree of height. The motivation for assuming that degree-functions of negative adjectives are reversed compared to the functions of their positive antonyms is the assumption represented by the entailment relation: *Musa is taller than Audu* iff *Audu is shorter*

than Musa. The ordering between the degrees assigned to two individuals by *short* is reversed in comparison with the ordering between the degrees assigned to them by *tall*.

On a reversed ordering of the scale, measuring the degree from infinity to the maximal degree of height of an individual, we get a greater-than relation in (123) where Musa's shortness-degrees exceed the amount of shortness-degrees that Audu possesses (124).

- (123) *Musa ka dɔgɔ ka tɛmɛ Audu kan.*
 Musa COP short INF surpass Audu POSTP
 'Musa is shorter than Audu.'
 (Lit.) 'Musa is short to surpass Audu.'

- (124) i $\llbracket \text{Audu } \langle \text{height} \rangle \text{ kan} \rrbracket = \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu})$
 ii $\llbracket \text{tɛmɛ} \rrbracket = \lambda d'. \lambda d. d > d'$
 iii $\llbracket \text{tɛmɛ Audu kan} \rrbracket = \lambda d. d > \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu})$
 iv $\llbracket \langle \text{PRO} \rangle \text{ tɛmɛ Audu kan} \rrbracket = d > (\text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu}))(d)$
 v $\llbracket \text{IP} \rrbracket = 1$ iff $d > \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu})$
 vi $\llbracket \text{ka tɛmɛ Audu kan} \rrbracket = \lambda d. d > \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu})$
 vii $\text{RESTRICT}(\llbracket \text{dɔgɔ} \rrbracket, \llbracket \text{FinP} \rrbracket) = \lambda d. \lambda x. \text{short}(x) \geq d$
 viii $\llbracket \text{dɔgɔ ka tɛmɛ Audu kan} \rrbracket = \lambda d. \lambda x. \text{short}(x) \geq d \ \& \ \wedge \ d > \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu})$
 ix $\text{EC}(\llbracket \text{dɔgɔ ka tɛmɛ Audu kan} \rrbracket) = \lambda x. \exists d. \text{short}(x) \geq d \ \wedge \ \wedge \ d > \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu})$
 x $\llbracket \text{Musa dɔgɔ ka tɛmɛ Audu kan} \rrbracket = \exists d. \text{short}(\text{Musa}) \geq d \ \wedge \ \wedge \ d > \text{HEIGHT}(\text{Audu})$
 xi = 1 iff there is a degree to which Musa is short that exceeds the degree of Audu's height (shortness extent).

The truth conditions of (124) state in (xi) that there is a degree of shortness that Musa reaches which exceeds the maximum degree of height that Audu reaches on a negative extent.

For cases that involve negation, we saw that a feature of Mande languages is the process of commutation of negation (Creissels 2020) (see section 4.1 for details). Since negation cannot be overtly expressed in its base position (as it is a negation of the verb), it commutes to a higher position in the tree, the I' head, instead negating the respective grammatical marker. However, interpreting the negation in (125) semantically low, will yield the wrong truth conditions as in (126). The result would be a negation that targets only exceed, flipping the greater-than relation from ">" to "<".

- (125) *Musa ma jan ka tɛmɛ Audu kan.*
 Musa NEG.COP tall INF surpass Audu POSTP
 'Musa is not taller than Audu.'

- (126) Musa $\exists d_1$ [COP d^1 -tall [NEG [d^1 surpass height(Audu)]]]
 TC: There is a degree to which Musa is tall which does not surpass the maximum degree of Audu's height.

(126) would be true even if Musa was taller than Audu, since it only describes a situation where Musa has any degree which does not surpass Audu's maximum degree of height. However, if negation is interpreted semantically higher, scoping in front of the existential operator instead of below it, we get the right truth conditions as in (127).

- (127) Musa [NEG[$\exists d_1$ [COP d^1 -tall [[d^1 surpass height(Audu)]]]]]
 TC: There is no degree to which Musa is tall which surpasses the maximum degree of Audu's height.

With the structure of the scope of negation in place, we can proceed with the derivation as in (128).

- (128) i $\llbracket \text{Audu} \langle \text{janya} \rangle \text{kan} \rrbracket = \text{height}(\text{Audu})$
 ii $\llbracket \text{teme} \rrbracket = \lambda d'. \lambda d. d > d'$
 iii $\llbracket \text{teme} \rrbracket(\llbracket \text{Audu kan} \rrbracket) = [\lambda d'. \lambda d. d > d'](\text{height}(\text{Audu}))$
 iv $\llbracket \text{teme Audu kan} \rrbracket(\llbracket \langle \text{PRO} \rangle \rrbracket) = [\lambda d. d > \text{height}(\text{Audu})](d)$
 v $\llbracket \text{IP} \rrbracket = 1$ iff $d > \text{height}(\text{Audu})$
 vi $\llbracket \text{ka} \rrbracket(\llbracket \text{teme Audu kan} \rrbracket) = \lambda d. d > \text{height}(\text{Audu})$
 vii $\llbracket \text{jan} \rrbracket = \lambda d. \lambda x. \text{tall}(x) \geq d$
 viii $\text{RESTRICT}(\llbracket \text{jan} \rrbracket, \llbracket \text{IP} \rrbracket) = \lambda d. \lambda x. \text{height}(x) \geq d \wedge d > \text{height}(\text{Audu})$
 ix $\llbracket \text{jan ka teme Audu kan} \rrbracket = \lambda d. \lambda x. \text{jan}(x) \geq d \wedge d > \text{height}(\text{Audu})$
 x $\text{EC}(\llbracket \text{jan ka teme Audu kan} \rrbracket) = \exists d. \lambda x. \text{age}(x) \geq d \wedge d > \text{height}(\text{Audu})$
 xi $\text{NEG}(\exists d. \lambda x. \text{age}(x) \geq d \wedge d > \text{height}(\text{Audu}))$
 xii $\llbracket \text{ma jan ka teme Audu kan} \rrbracket(\llbracket \text{Musa} \rrbracket) = [\neg \exists d. \text{tall}(x) \geq d \wedge d > \text{height}(\text{Audu})](\text{Musa})$
 xiii $\llbracket \text{Musa ma jan ka teme Audu kan} \rrbracket(\llbracket \text{Musa} \rrbracket) = \neg \exists d. \text{tall}(\text{Musa}) \geq d \wedge d > \text{height}(\text{Audu})$
 xiv = 1 iff there is no degree of tallness that Musa reaches that exceeds the maximum degree of height of Audu.

Until step (xi) the derivation proceeds parallel to the positive case. The matrix predicate with *tall* combines with the infinitive phrase via RESTRICT. After existential closure over the degree argument of the adjective, negation applies in step (xi) and scopes above the whole constituent. This is spelled out in step (xii) with the negated counterpart of the copula *ka*. Lastly, we feed the subject *Musa* into the derivation in (xiii) and get the truth conditions in (xiv).

4.4 Summary

The table in this subsection provides an overview of the explicit constructions that I investigated so far, their types, features, and the kinds of arguments they take. Native speaker judgments aided the determination of the felicity of the combination with argument types. The table will receive further updates, after treating the implicit constructions in section 5.

Comparative Constructions			
Operator	Type	Features	Arguments
<i>Ka tɛmɛ</i>	Explicit intransitive	Non-finite	Complex nouns, MP's, adjectival OR adverbial matrix predicates
<i>Be tɛmɛ</i>	Explicit intransitive	Imperfective	Complex nouns or MP's
<i>Dan</i>	Explicit transitive	Main verb	Nominalized arguments or MP's

The table shows that the infinitive construction *ka tɛmɛ* felicitously combines with complex nouns and measure phrases. It is subordinated either by an adjectival or an adverbial matrix predicate. The bare *tɛmɛ* construction is likewise restricted to nominal arguments in its standard and may take nominalized properties in a possessive relation with an individual as its subject. Measure phrases are taken to denote NP's of type $\langle d \rangle$ which are non-quantifying. The bare construction is often preceded by a habitual marker, making it imperfective, but may also be subject to other tense or aspect markers. The main verb construction with *dan* strictly licenses nominal argument and nothing else. Properties or verbs appear in nominalized form either with overt or covert possessive markers preceding them and indicates a possessive relation with the subject. Additionally, adjectives in Jula are lexically evaluative and parallel English adjectives.

In general, the analysis show that the explicit construction can comfortably be fitted with a 2-place analysis that compares two degrees as in (129). This analysis is motivated by the syntactic and semantic structure.

$$(129) \quad \llbracket \text{exceed} \rrbracket = \lambda d'. \lambda d. d > d'$$

The chapters preceding the formal analysis sections provide the theoretic foundation for the uniform analysis posited for the 'exceed' in Jula. In summary, I have argued for the phrasal nature of *tɛmɛ* based on the type of arguments it takes. Diagnostics from different approaches like the parameter approach by Beck (2009), as well as the individual/ degree distinction by Kennedy (2007) show that Jula makes use of degrees in the semantics and that degrees, derived via measure functions on nominalized properties, can enter the derivation directly as arguments.

In the next section, an additional distinction is made in comparison between explicit and implicit structures and I turn to investigate the underlying syntax and semantics of implicit comparison in Jula.

5 Implicit Comparison

We find that Jula makes use of two implicit comparative structures. The distribution parallels its explicit counterparts to an extent. The first construction is an infinitive form of 'consider' composed with an adjectival matrix predicate (135). The second is a comitative construction, likewise composed with an adjectival matrix predicate (137).

- (130) *Ka Kala jati, Taro ka kərə.*
 INF Kala consider, Taro COP old
 'Compared to/ considering Kala, Taro is old.'
 (Lit.) 'Taro is old considering Kala.'

- (131) *Taro ka kərə ni Kala ye.*
 Taro COP old CONJ Kala POSTP
 'Taro is old compared to Kala.'

Following the intuitions in Kennedy (2007a), the main difference between explicitness and implicitness hinges on the form of the adjective. While explicit comparison makes use of explicit verbal (i.e. 'exceed') or inflectional (i.e. '-er') morphology, implicit comparison often only uses the positive form of the adjective and is context sensitive. Context-dependency entails that in order for the comparison to be felicitous, the compared objects have to differ substantially from one another. By using crisp judgment tests that create an environment which is minimally vague, I can determine whether a comparison construction is implicit (Kennedy 2007a; Bochnak 2018). The explicit and implicit distinction is important in order to conduct a proper analysis, as they vary distinctly in their underlying semantics and the arguments that they take (Kennedy 2007a).

In the next section I examine the two constructions above using the crisp judgment diagnostics and continue to describe the syntax and distribution. This is followed by a formal semantic analysis of implicit comparison construction in Jula and concluded with a section summary.

5.1 Crisp Judgments

Crisp judgments contexts are contexts in which the items that are compared only differ marginally and are very similar in measurement. Implicit comparison by virtue needs one object to be

substantially set apart from the other, and should be unacceptable in a context that specifies only a slight difference. The necessity for a differential gap in measurement has been coined the similarity constraint (Graff 2000; Kennedy 2007b, 2011). This assumption stems from the non-trivial partitioning on the adjective’s domain, an inherent feature of implicit comparison that entails that the positive and negative extension of an adjective is non-empty (Klein 1980) (for more details see 2.1). This entails that the respective parts of implicit comparison *x is A* and *compared to y* come with different truth conditions, namely that *x is A* and *y is not*. Under the assumption that (135) and (137) truly are implicit comparatives, they should be infelicitous in such a context. This prediction is borne out for the two implicit constructions in Jula, as (132) and (133) show respectively.

- (132) CONTEXT: MUSA IS 1.64M AND AUDU IS 1.65M TALL.
- | | |
|------------------------------------|---------------------|
| a. ✓ Audu ka jan ka tɛmɛ Musa kan. | EXPLICIT |
| b. # Audu ka jan ni Musa ye. | IMPLICIT COMITATIVE |
-
- (133) CONTEXT: CIRCLE A IS RED, CIRCLE B IS A LIGHTER SHADE OF RED.
- | | |
|--------------------------------|---------------------|
| a. ✓ A ka wulen ka tɛmɛ B kan. | EXPLICIT |
| b. # Ka B jati, A ka wulen. | IMPLICIT INFINITIVE |

Using these diagnostics, (132a) and (133a) are felicitous, while the implicit b) options are not. Using the comitative construction is infelicitous in a context where Musa and Audu only differ marginally in height. Similarly, in (133) the infinitive implicit construction is infelicitous if both circles are red and only differ in a shade of redness.

The availability of differential measure phrases is another diagnostic criteria to determine implicit structures. Measure phrases override the semantics of the positive form, because the meaning of measurement allows them to combine directly with the predicate (Kennedy 2007b). Hence, a gradable predicate is generated that is no longer context dependent. Since the derivation of the implicit comparison manipulates the contextual comparison standard, once the measurement combines with the predicate the context becomes fixed and can no longer be subject to manipulation, resulting in an infelicitous phrase like (134).

- (134) # Audu is 10 cm tall compared to Musa.

Both constructions, infinitive and comitative, are infelicitous in any combination with measure phrases. I find one exception, where a measure phrase may be fronted in combination with the comitative construction. However, the felicity of this construction may, similarly to Yoruba, hinge on a difference of the type of measure phrases in Jula. This example is left for future investigation.⁹

⁹

5.2 Syntax and Distribution

Ni ye and *ka jati* have no dedicated degree morphology or other periphrastic structures, but instead make use of comparison that is not overtly expressed by comparative morphology and can be modified by context.

5.2.1 The Infinitive Construction

The infinitive implicit construction exhibits a pattern that is similar to its explicit counterpart. The subject appears together with the comparison dimension in an adjectival matrix predicate which may either precede or follow the infinitive phrase. Unlike the explicit infinitive construction, the infinitive phrase (135) may move as a whole and be fronted.

- (135) *Ka Kala jati, Taro ka kɔɔ.*
 INF Kala consider, Taro COP old
 ‘Compared to Kala, Taro is old.’
 (Lit.) ‘Taro is old considering Kala.’

Following Kiemtoré (2022) and for the purpose of a uniform analysis, I assume that there is a covert PRO-subject in the infinitive phrase, which resides in the specifier position of an unpronounced I-head. *Kala* is the internal argument of the verb ‘consider’ and has moved to a position above the verb, which is line with the SOV word order in Jula.

(136)

-
- (1) *5cm le be Hawa surun-ya ni Fofana ye.*
 5cm FOC HAB Hawa shorten CONJ Fofana PostP
 ‘It is 5cm that Hawa’s shortness is compared to Fofana.’

5.2.2 The Comitative Construction

The second implicit construction involves a comitative structure. The morpheme *ni* has the nature of a conjunction without additional postpositions or other grammatical markers. In a combination with the postposition *ye* that introduces the object of the phrase, *ni* receives a comitative interpretation as in (138)-(139) and preceded by adjectival predicates it results in a comparative (137).

- (137) *Taro ka kɔrɔ ni Kala ye.*
 Taro COP old CONJ Kala POSTP
 ‘Taro is old compared to Kala.’

This shift from a comitative to a comparative interpretation in combination with adjectives is a feature in many Mande languages (Creissels 2020).

- (138) *A be ja dilan ni kulɛri ye.*
 3SG HAB picture make CONJ color POSTP.
 ‘She paints with colors.’

- (139) *Gninan-w be boli ni jakumani ye*
 Mouse-PL HAB run CONJ cat POSTP.
 The mice are running with the cat.’
 ‘The mice are running with the cat.’

For adjectival predicates, *ni...ye* can be in free variation with the infinitival comparative *ka...tɛmɛ* as long as no overt measurements like MPs are present.

A syntactic tree is provided for (137) in (140):

- (140)

5.3 Formal Analysis

In the beginning of this section I have provided examples of the two implicit comparative structures that I find in Jula. By applying diagnostic criteria such as crisp judgment tests and the combination with measure phrases both the infinitive and the comitative construction can clearly be distinguished as implicit comparison. This was followed by a syntactic analysis and a description of the structure and distribution of both constructions. Building on the background on implicit comparison from section 2 and the formal framework from Hohaus (2015) I posit a formal analysis for the two constructions.

The previous section explored how a compositional analysis of explicit comparison in Jula may be approached by investigating different topics like gradability and evaluativity. By situating a comparative phrase in different contexts that require the matrix predicate to encode evaluativity, I found that adjectives (and by extension adverbs) in Jula are lexically evaluative and may receive a lexical entry as in (141).

$$(141) \quad \llbracket tall \rrbracket = \lambda d. \lambda x. HEIGHT(x) \geq d$$

The infinitive construction and the comitative construction have in common that both are preceded by (or combined with) an adjectival matrix predicate as in ‘Taro is old’. The unbound c variable which denotes a contextually set standard of that property and varies with regard to the situations the phrase is uttered in, is now equal to the comparative denoted by the infinitive or comitative phrase.

$$(142) \quad \begin{array}{l} Ka \ Kala \ jati, \quad Taro \ ka \ kərɔ. \\ \text{INF Kala consider, Taro COP old.} \\ \text{‘Taro is old compared to Kala.’} \\ \text{(Lit.) ‘Considering Kala, Taro is old.’} \end{array}$$

I start with the denotation of the infinitive constituent ‘to consider Kala’ from the example (135) here repeated in (142). The denotation of the verb is to consider a specific individual x in a situation s . Adding the individual *Kala* for x leaves us with possible situations in which Kala is considered (ii).

$$(143) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{i) } \llbracket To \ consider \rrbracket = \lambda x_{\langle e \rangle}. \lambda s_{\langle s \rangle}. \exists \mu_{\langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle}. [\mu(x)(s)] \\ \text{ii) } \llbracket To \ consider \ Kala \rrbracket = \lambda s_{\langle s \rangle}. \exists \mu_{\langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle}. [\mu(Kala)(s)] \end{array}$$

A frame per definitionem limits the possible situations which arise (Hohaus 2015). In the case of Jula, restricting the evaluation situations to situations which contain Kala. By applying a MIN-operator (144), possible situations are further restricted to the subset of situations that contain *Taro* and *Kala*. The only possible dimension they may be compared in is the dimension of AGE which comes from the adjectival matrix predicate. The result is a situation in which *Taro* is considered old with regard to *Kala*.

$$(144) \quad \llbracket MIN \rrbracket = \lambda p_{\langle s, t \rangle}. \lambda s_{\langle s \rangle}. p(s) \wedge \neg \exists s' [s' \prec s \wedge p(s')]$$

$$(145) \quad \llbracket Ka \text{ Kala jati, Taro ka } k\acute{o}r\acute{o}, 7 \rrbracket = \lambda s : \text{MIN}(\lambda s'.old(Kala))(s). \exists d.old(s)(Taro) \geq d \wedge d > g(7)$$

The constituent $g(7)$ specifies the contextual threshold and is equal to the content specified by the function $g(7)$, in this case the comparison with Kala where g is a function of a dimension of age. With the presence of a comparison clause, this threshold is fixed to the evaluation situation. When the comparison clause is absent, this threshold is generically fixed.

The difference between the infinitive *Ka...jati* and the comitative *Ni...ye* construction lies in the specification of the presupposed situation. The comitative is more underspecified, while the presupposed situation in the infinitive implicit construction only selects for situations that contain 'Kala'. The function specification for g is the same - the only applicable dimension to compare in is *age*, as only values from the same dimension may be compared.

5.4 Summary

An update to the table presented in section 4 now includes the two implicit constructions. I find that the comitative is restricted to combining with adjectives and individuals, otherwise it receives an interpretation as a conjunction. The second construction seems likewise to license adjectives, but is considerably less common.

Comparative Constructions			
Operator	Type	Features	Arguments
<i>Ka tēmε</i>	Explicit intransitive	Non-finite, evaluative	Complex nouns, MP's, adjectival OR adverbial matrix predicates
<i>Be tēmε</i>	Explicit intransitive	Imperfective	Complex nouns or MP's
<i>Dan</i>	Explicit transitive	Main verb	Nominalized arguments or MP's
<i>Ka jati</i>	Implicit	Non-finite, non-trivial partitioning	Individuals, adjectival matrix predicates
<i>Ni ye</i>	Implicit	Comitative	Adjectival predicates, Individuals

Table 4: Features of Comparative Constructions in Jula

By using diagnostics such as crisp judgments tests, I have shown that the comitative and the *consider*-construction are implicit comparatives. Formalizing the implicit comparative construction in a style based on Hohaus (2015) analysis of contextual comparatives proves to be fruitful to describe the Jula data. I have suggested a formal analysis that may, with minor modifications, be

considered for both constructions, indicating similar structures concerning argument restrictions and evaluativity. By applying a minimum-selection process to the framework specification of sets of situations, an analysis can successfully be posited for both constructions. One construction which has received considerably less attention is the adverbial implicit comparative. However, this construction is left for future research. In the next section, I briefly touch upon superlatives and equatives in Jula, and situate them in the formal framework that has been established in this thesis.

6 Superlatives and Equatives

Looking at the comparative morphology involved in comparatives and superlatives in English, there seem to be substantial, at least ontological, differences between the two. Standing accounts posit different lexical entries for the comparative *-er* and the superlative *-est* (Heim 2001), assuming that the superlative is an operator independent of the comparative. But cross-linguistic research suggests that the superlative, in fact contains the comparative (Bobaljik 2012). In *exceed*-comparatives the case is more transparent. Lacking dedicated comparative (and superlative) morphology, the superlative meaning is derived from the comparative form, by taking the same structure and a universal quantifier in the comparison standard. A universal quantifier *bee* is the standard posited in the infinitive construction.

- (146) *Fanga be n fe ka teme bee kan.*
 Strength COP 1SG.SUBJ POSTP INF surpass all POSTP.
 ‘I am the strongest.’
 (Lit.) ‘The strength that is with me surpasses everyone.’

In the superlative example (146), the combination with a universal quantifier elicits a meaning of exhaustivity. The interpretation is one where the subject in relation to the standard possesses the greatest degree of a property. With adjectival matrix predicates the comitative construction may be used to express the superlative (147).

- (147) *Hawa ka jan ni bee ye.*
 Hawa COP tall CONJ all POSTP.
 ‘Hawa is the tallest of all.’
- (148) *Fofana be folike ka teme o bee kan.*
 Fofana HAB play INF surpass 3PL all POSTP.
 ‘Fofana plays the best of them all.’
- (149) *Ne le be se jadilan la ka teme bee kan.*
 1EMP PART HAB be.able painting POSTP INF surpass everyone POSTP.
 ‘I have more skill painting than anyone else.’/ I am the only one with this much skill painting.’

Equatives show a different pattern. Instead of a verb denoting the sense of *surpass* and establishing an ordering relation along a scale, the adjectival phrase ‘... is equal’ *ka kan* establishes an equality relationship between two objects (150). Another version comes with the adjective ‘same’ *kelen* (151). The third construction is more pragmatic and relies on contextual interpretation to elicit an equative meaning. The interpretation for (152) is idiomatic in the sense of "there is a saying that..." object A has a property equal in skill to object B. When describing Kofi and Ama, for instance "One might say that they drive equally fast." or that "Their degree of speed when driving is the same."

(150) *An (bεε) janyan ka kan.*
 1PL (all) height COP equal
 (Lit.) ‘Our heights are equal.’

(151) *An (bεε) janyan bε kelen ye.*
 1PL (all) height COP same POSTP
 (Lit.) ‘Our heights (that are with us) are the same.’

(152) *Kofi be mobili boli joona i ko Ama.*
 Kofi HAB car run fast 2SG say Ama
 ‘Kofi and Ama drive equally fast.’
 (Lit.) ‘It is said/ you might say that Kofi and Ama drive equally fast.’

In general, Jula expresses equatives in two ways: by constructing an adjectival matrix clause where the subject consists of a possessive phrase governing a possessor and a nominalized property while simultaneously supplying the comparison standard and an idiomatic expression where the equality relation is pragmatically inferred, possibly denoting a subjunctive mood, (150)-(151).

7 General Discussion

7.1 On Macro-Parameters

Languages can develop some degree morphemes without grammaticalizing an entire degree system. Bochnak et al. (2015) account for the range of languages that grammaticalize one or few degree morphemes. Where otherwise –DSP languages with some degree morphology are still treated as –DSP, there is a notable gap in classification on the binary DSP distinction and it accounts only for a subset of languages where the gradable predicate interacts with degree morphology or any other sentential constructs. Tswefap and Yoruba are examples where the verb interacts with degree morphology and becomes gradable, while adjectives do not. This behavior would be unexpected under an approach that classifies by binary macro-parameters. Clem (2019) proposes that the respective EXCEED in Tswefap subcategorizes for a verb in order to express gradable comparatives. However, any constraint to the category of gradable predicates (like verbs) would undo the status as a macro-parameter.

Similar restraints become obvious in consideration of the second parameter: degree abstraction.

Howell (2013) showed that Yoruba can lack all subsequent structures that indicate a positive DAP-setting but still have degree abstraction as a circumstance of other factors like modified numeral phrases. Likewise, the presence of the DAP-requirements (like subcomparatives) does not obligatorily entail that a language has degree abstraction. In a case where the standard consists of a complex noun or a clause, the derivation of a degree, even when it is on a different scale than in the matrix clause, is derived locally and does not provide proof for degree abstraction. The Jula-data has similarly shown that other diagnostics are necessary to provide evidence for certain structures in the language. A classification that hinges purely on binary parameters might prove to be too weak to tease apart the underlying structure of comparatives in languages that deviate from the standard functional morpheme cluster.

7.2 The Underlying Semantics of Gradable Predicates

The argument that gradable predicates take as much weight in the determination of the operator as the other way around is a natural one. There is an interplay between the operator and the gradable predicates it combines with. But how do we determine the structure of gradable predicates? Can one assume a unified underlying semantics for gradable adjectives, relational nouns, gradable verbs and adverbs that interacts with the operator? And is it possible to determine whether all categories are derived from one main category? We could of course just call these property concept lexemes (Deal & Hohaus 2019) and give them a unified semantics that maps properties to degrees. Variation comes about by deriving the types from $\langle d, \langle e, t \rangle \rangle$ to for example $\langle e, d \rangle$ for nominalized properties. A question that remains is how we can determine whether a property makes use of degrees.

Certain restrictions can be observed concerning what kind of noun-adjective pairs may be constructed. Not all nouns which are modifiable can be generalized to combine with all adjectives. In that case, what determines the restrictions on which adjectives may modify which nouns? Copenstake (2013) describes two approaches: A probability/frequency approach and a denotation approach. The former, the frequency with which an adjective combines with a noun (or vice versa) in natural language determines the probability with which combinations are felicitous. For example, the adjective ‘colorful’ more frequently appears in combination with nouns denoting physical entities, rather than abstract objects. On the denotation approach the noun licenses the type of adjective it combines with.

In the chapter on adverbial modification, I argued for a dimensional slot (spatial, temporal or otherwise) that is part of the lexical meaning of all verbs that can be modified by adverbs. Possibly, this can be applied to nouns as well. All nouns which may be modified by an adjective have as part of their lexical meaning a dimension which is underspecified by default. Then this leaves the degreefulness to adjectives and adverbs with covert underspecified degree variables for all modifiable verbs and nouns. Relational nouns, by transitivity and axiomatic definition (Nicholas 2004), become gradable by denoting a measure function similar to the adjectives they are derived from.

7.3 The Semantics of EXCEED

It is argued in this thesis that the Jula exceed-comparatives in fact need a 2-place analysis, hinging on the requirements of the infinitive phrase, Jula having degree semantics, and phrasal exceed-comparatives. Cross-linguistically, it is eminent that different languages require and employ different comparative operators. Although it is obvious that the syntax-semantics mapping is not as straightforward as is laid out in the literature, a more languages are added to the informational body of comparative research, it becomes blatant that an analysis hinging entirely on the semantics of the comparative operator is too simple to be successful. The gradable predicate, its type and its underlying semantics, as well as the general typological make-up of a language, are all equally important for the analysis of exceed-comparatives.

Exceed-comparatives in the literature have been shown to be phrasal due to the nature of verbal EXCEED as well constraints on the type of the comparison standard, and have received a 3-place analysis. An exception is given by Bochnak (2018) for Luganda, who shows that an analysis with three arguments derives the same truth conditions as an analysis that takes two degree arguments for Luganda exceed-comparatives. The main argument comes from the presence of subcomparatives, which by Beck's (2009) diagnostic criteria do not license clausal material and therefore, cannot receive a clausal analysis but still supply two arguments. However, Luganda similar to Jula, nominalizes its properties and gradable predicates and when both comparison standard and matrix predicate supply a nominalized complex NP, the degree arguments are simply derived locally. It would be interesting to see how the construction with an embedded infinitive in Luganda would fare. The way the infinitive comparative in Jula is structured, it is in need of a 2-place analysis. The 3-place analysis is no option as it would leave the gradable predicate stranded in the matrix clause and unable to access the argument in the comparison standard.

The table provides an overview of a small portion of exceed-comparatives and their analysis. We see that the majority has received a 3-place analysis. Some are argued to have a 2-place semantics additionally, but for now it seems that Jula is the only language which only has a 2-place semantics for comparatives.

One might also consider the factor of relevancy: What are the reasons a language would employ a 2-place semantics and a more complicated 3-place semantics for the same construction, unless to express a more complex matter? A question that also remains is whether comparatives are subject to reduction operations or whether they can handle a direct analysis. The direct analysis presupposes no quantification, while reduction analyses assume quantification that licenses ellipsis and creates sets of degrees by abstracting over them. However, EXCEED is not quantifying. In the derivation we are left with a type $\langle t \rangle$ at the boundary of the infinitive phrase. I need to abstract over a degree at the boundary in order get an argument that can further the derivation. However, then one encounters an AP which under normal circumstances can access both arguments (individuals) and relate them to degrees on a scale. Due to the embedding in a subordinate infinitive this option remains closed. Instead the predicate and the FinP are combined via RESTRICT, leaving us with an open degree slot which is existentially bound.

Language	Interface	
	3-place	2-place
Yoruba (Howell 2013)	✓	
Tswefap (Clem 2013)	✓	
Luganda (Bochnak 2018)	✓	✓
Ndebele (Weingartz 2024)	✓	
Hausa (Zimmermann 2011)	✓	
Mandarin (Liu 2010)	✓	✓
Moore (Gong & Coppock 2024)	✓	
Jula		✓

Table 5: Analysis of exceed-comparatives in the literature

7.4 Jula adjectives are true adjectives

An important point that has been made for Jula comparative constructions is the presence of evaluativity. This feature has not been attested for (or investigated) in comparatives in any other African language. Still, this is not surprising, as evaluativity can be found in other constructions other than positive adjective phrases, namely equatives, question-phrases and measure phrases (Rett 2015). However, insofar as the polarity and boundedness of adjectives determines evaluativity, relative adjectives (that need a contextually specified standard) are, similar to English adjectives, evaluative in Jula.

This pattern does not hold for adjectives which have been derived from verbs in Jula. Nominalized properties also belong in this category, as they already denote a maximal degree of a property. However, evaluativity (at least in Jula) seems to only apply to proper adjectives and may serve as a diagnostic to determine which adjectives have been derived and which have not.

8 Conclusion

Comparatives have regained a lot of focus, especially among formal semanticists. The data on Jula comparatives contributes to a broad puzzle, where established claims have persisted that are subject to and due for revisions. Following the compositional approach to semantics, I add supporting evidence to the topic of the syntax-semantics interface of phrasal comparatives and comparative operators, and to the semantics of gradable predicates in the scope of negation and polarity. Standing assumptions regarding the phrasal nature of exceed-comparatives do not hold for the Jula data and that a mapping with a 3-place semantics cannot adequately explain the constructions presented. Instead, I propose to treat the exceed-comparatives as 2-place oper-

ators. Constructions with differential comparatives, subcomparatives, comparison with degrees illustrate that Jula has degree semantics, and using similar diagnostics as Howell for Yoruba (2013), I also provided evidence that Jula has degree abstraction, despite a lack of scope ambiguities. With these two macro parameters in place, the Jula data can be fitted with a unified 2-place analysis that is based on the comparison of degrees, providing the barest of all semantics. This unified analysis is underlined by providing detailed descriptions and formal analyses of the syntax as well as the semantics of the explicit and the implicit constructions in Jula in a compositional manner.

In further investigation, I looked at how Jula comparatives dealt with antonyms and probed at the underlying semantics of gradable predicates. I found that the presence of a positive operator, coined an evaluative marker by Rett (2007), a term I adopted, is present in adjectives in Jula. This pertains for comparative constructions with both positive and negative polar relative adjectives like *tall/ short*. More constructions than simple copular adjective phrases may be evaluative, as equatives, *wh*-questions and MPs, but are left for future research. We have seen that negation in a comparative in Jula is expressed syntactically high, as a negated version of the TAM-marker preceding the gradable predicate, but that semantically it scopes above the existential operator binding the degree argument. This allowed us to derive the correct truth conditions for both positive and negative cases. In further analyses, I have also shown that the initially developed two-place semantics for the adjectival infinitive construction can be transported to the adverbial cases as well as the other explicit comparative construction explored in this thesis. The two-place analysis that compares two degrees can felicitously fit explicit comparative constructions in Jula providing a uniform semantic analysis. I have also probed at an initial analysis for implicit comparison in Jula building on previous works, but realize that more data and more research is needed for a satisfactory analysis.

Overall, the thesis makes several distinct claims, which are supported by the findings and subsequently, by the analyses. The results endorse the effect of polarity, negation and a distinct underlying semantics for gradable adjectives. There are still a lot of open questions and research opportunities for Jula and *exceed*-comparatives in general.

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Appendices

.1 Figures and Tables

	Marker	Meaning
Tense	ka	adjectival copula
	bɛ	locative copula
Aspect	be	habitual, progressive
	ká	subjunctive
	bena	future

Table 1: Tense-Aspect markers in Jula

Adjective Pairs	
Positive/ Negative	Meaning
jan /surun	tall/long /short
bɔn /dɔgɔ	big /small
guli /fignɛ	heavy /light
kɔrɔ /dɔgɔ	old /young
gbɛɛ	expensive
teli	fast/speedy
gni	nice
dun	deep

Table 2: Most Common Adjectives in Jula

Comparative Constructions			
Operator	Type	Features	Arguments
<i>Ka tɛmɛ</i>	Explicit intransitive	Non-finite, evaluative	Complex nouns, MP's, adjectival OR adverbial matrix predicates
<i>Be tɛmɛ</i>	Explicit intransitive	Imperfective	Complex nouns or MP's
<i>Dan</i>	Explicit transitive	Main verb	Nominalized arguments or MP's
<i>Ka jati</i>	Implicit	Non-finite, non-trivial partitioning	Individuals, adjectival matrix predicates
<i>Ni ye</i>	Implicit	Comitative	Adjectival predicates, Individuals

Table 3: Features of Comparative Constructions in Jula

Forms		Functional Domains
Positive	Negative	
be	tɛ	Existential/ locative copula
ka	ma/ man	Predicative/ adjectival copula
Affirmative	Negative	
be	te	Imperfective - habitualis

Table 4: Positive and negated TAM-amrkers

Language	Interface	
	3-place	2-place
Yoruba (Howell 2013)	✓	
Tswefap (Clem 2013)	✓	
Luganda (Bochnak 2018)	✓	✓
Ndebele (Weingartz 2019)	✓	
Hausa (Zimmermann 2011)	✓	
Mandarin (Liu 2010)	✓	✓
Moore (Gong & Coppock 2024)	✓	
Jula		✓

Table 5: Analysis of exceed-comparatives in the literature